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Master: Databases and Software technologies

Project

Data Warehouse & Business Intelligence

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1. Analysis module

1.1 Description of the chosen model and the objectives of the application

To carry out this project, we chose as the theme the management of a chain of fitness centers that offer training services as well as highlighting the results at certain time intervals.

The database operations are focused on customers. They have the possibility to purchase subscriptions with different durations and prices. Each training session is carried out individually, with or without the guidance of a fitness trainer.

The database stores data specific to trainers, the gyms where they work, and the available fitness programs.

The usefulness of this model is to monitor results, both the results of individual clients and the fitness chain, as results/cost reports for clients and profit/cost reports for the gym chain can be generated.

The database contains 10 tables. Within them, 3 constraints were applied, the PRIMARY KEY constraint, the FOREIGN KEY constraint, and the Unique constraint.

The PRIMARY KEY constraint uniquely identifies each record. Thus, in each of the 10 tables, there is a column, the first column, defined as the PRIMARY KEY. The existence of the unique identifier at the table level allows operations on any record when operations are desired on it and only it.

The FOREIGN KEY constraint establishes a foreign key relationship between a column in a table and a column in a referenced table. In tables that contain data about service purchases and customer outcomes, foreign keys are used to generate individual reports about each customer.

The UNIQUE constraint ensures that all values in a column are different.

1.2 OLTP database diagrams

1.2.1. ER diagram of the OLTP database

1.2.2. Conceptual diagram of OLTP database

1.3 Star schema

1.4 Description of the fields required for each table in the D.W. database and how to populate them with information from the OLTP database

The D.W. database consists of 5 dimension tables and 2 fact tables. The 5 dimension tables are “Customers”, “Trainers”, “Subscriptions”, “Time” and “Locations”. The 2 fact tables are “Subscriptions_History” and “Sessions_History”.

The “Customers” dimension table has the following fields:

- **id** - Primary Key – Unique identifier for each record in the “Customers” dimension table. **Auto-incremented** using the “**tdw_customers_seq**” sequence.
- **Customer_id** - Unique identifier taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database, representing the primary key of that table. The transfer is done using the “**tdw_customers_insert**” procedure.
- **First_name** – The customer’s last name, taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tdw_customers_insert**” procedure.

- **Last_name** – The customer’s first name, taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_customers_insert**” procedure.
- **Email** – Unique Identifier – The customer’s email address, taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_customers_insert**” procedure.
- **Phone_number** – The customer’s phone number, taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_customers_insert**” procedure.
- **Date_of_birth** – Date of birth of the customer, taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_customers_insert**” procedure.
- **Gender** – Gender of the customer, taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_customers_insert**” procedure.
- **Has_health_issues** – Variable that determines whether the customer can purchase services with or without a trainer. Taken from the “Customers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_customers_insert**” procedure.

The “**Trainers**” dimension table has the following fields:

- **Id** – Primary Key – Unique identifier for each record in the “Trainers” dimension table. **Auto-incremented** using the “**tbdw_trainers_seq**” sequence.
- **Trainer_id** – Unique identifier taken from the Trainers table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure.
- **First_name** – The trainer’s last name, taken from the Trainers table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure.
- **Last_name** – The trainer’s first name, taken from the “Trainers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure.
- **Email** – The trainer’s email address, taken from the “Trainers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure.
- **Phone_number** – The trainer’s phone number, taken from the “Trainers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure.
- **Birth_date** – The trainer’s date of birth, taken from the “Trainers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure
- **Hire_date** – The trainer’s hire date, taken from the “Contracts” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure.

- **Contract_end_date** – The trainer’s contract end date, taken from the “Contracts” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.

- **Gender** – The gender of the trainer, taken from the “Trainers” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_trainers_insert**” procedure.

The “**Subscriptions**” dimension table has the following fields:

- **Id** – Primary Key – Unique identifier for each record in the “Subscriptions” dimension table. **Auto-incremented** using the “**tbdw_subscriptions_seq**” sequence.

- **Subscription_id** – Unique identifier taken from the “Subscriptions” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**” procedure.

- **Max_number_sessions** – Variable that specifies the maximum number of sessions available in the subscription, taken from the “Subscriptions” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**” procedure.

- **Title** – The name of the subscription, taken from the “Subscriptions” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the procedure “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.

- **Description** – Description of the subscription, taken from the “Subscriptions” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the procedure “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.

- **With_trainer** – Variable that specifies whether the subscription includes a personalized trainer. A customer who has health problems will not be able to purchase subscriptions unless they include a personal trainer. Taken from the “Subscriptions” table, the transfer is done using the “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**” procedure.

- **Max_number_days** – The variable specifies the maximum number of days the subscription is valid for. Taken from the “Subscriptions” table, the transfer is done using the “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**” procedure.

The “**Time**” dimension table has the following fields:

- **Timp_id** – Primary Key – Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.

- **An** – The year, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” variable from the “Time” dimension table. Extracted using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.

- **Semestru** – The semester, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column from the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Trimestru** – The quarter, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Luna** – The month, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated from the “timp_id” variable using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Saptamana_an** - The week of the year, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Saptamana_luna** – The week of the month, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Zi_an** – Day of the year, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated from the “timp_id” variable using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Zi_luna** – Day of the month, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Zi_saptamana** – Day of the week, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Zi_nume** – Day of the week, expressed by name, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.
- **Luna_nume** – Month of the year, expressed by name, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated procedure “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Weekend** – Variable used to specify whether the day associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column is considered a weekend day, by the value 1, or not by the value 0. Generated using procedure “**tbdw_time_insert**”.

- **An_bisect** – Variable used to specify whether the year associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column is considered a leap year, by the value 1, or not by the value 0. Generated using procedure “**tbdw_time_insert**”.

- **Saptamana_calendar** – Calendar week, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using procedure “**tbdw_time_insert**”.

- **Saptamana_an_business** – Week of the year, expressed numerically, associated with the date stored in the “timp_id” column of the “Time” dimension table. Generated using the “**tbdw_time_insert**” procedure.

The “**Locations**” dimension table has the following fields:

- **Id** - Primary Key – Unique identifier for each record in the “Locations” dimension table. **Auto-incremented** using the “**tbdw_locations_seq**” sequence.

- **Location_id** – Unique identifier taken from the “Locations” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_locations_insert**” procedure.

- **Capacity** – Column specifying the maximum number of customers who can use the fitness room at the same time. Value taken from the “Locations” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_locations_insert**” procedure

- **State_name** – The name of the county where the fitness center is located, taken from the “States” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_locations_insert**” procedure.

- **City_name** – The name of the city where the fitness center is located, taken from the “Cities” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_locations_insert**” procedure.

- **Address** – The address of the fitness center, taken from the “Locations” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_locations_insert**” procedure

- **City_id** – The ID identifier from the O.L.T.P. database of the city where the fitness center is located, taken from the “Cities” table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_locations_insert**” procedure.

- **State_id** – The ID identifier from the O.L.T.P. database of the county in which the fitness center location is located in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_locations_insert**” procedure.

The "Subscriptions_History" fact table has the following fields:

- **Id** - Primary Key – Unique identifier for each record in the "Subscriptions_History" fact table. **Auto-incremented** using the sequence "**tbdw_subscriptions_seq**".
- **Subscription_id** – Foreign Key – Identifier taken from the "Customers_Subscriptions" table in the O.L.T.P. database. Allows the connection between the "Subscriptions_History" and "Subscriptions" tables in the DW. The transfer is done using the "**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**" procedure.
- **Customer_Subscription_id** – Unique identifier taken from the "Customers_Subscriptions" table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the "**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**" procedure.
- **Customer_id** – Foreign Key - Identifier taken from the "Customers_Subscriptions" table in the O.L.T.P. database. Allows the connection between the "Subscriptions_History" and "Customers" tables in the DW. The transfer is done using the "**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**" procedure.
- **Start_time_id** – Foreign Key – Date from which the subscription takes effect. Taken from the "Customers_Subscriptions" table. Allows the connection between the "Subscriptions_history" and "Time" tables. The transfer is done using the "**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**" procedure
- **End_time_id** – Foreign Key – Last day of validity of the subscription. Taken from the "Customers_Subscriptions" table in the O.L.T.P. database. Allows the connection between the "Subscriptions_History" and "Time" tables. The transfer is done using the "**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**" procedure
- **Price** – The price of the subscription at the time of purchase, taken from the "Subscriptions" table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the "**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**" procedure

The "**Sessions_History**" fact table has the following fields:

- **Id** – Primary Key – Unique identifier for each record in the "Sessions_History" fact table. Auto-incremented using the "**tbdw_sessions_seq**" sequence.
- **Session_id** – Unique identifier taken from the "Sessions" table in the O.L.T.P. database. The transfer is done using the "**tbdw_sessions_history_insert**" procedure.
- **Customer_id** – Foreign Key - Identifier taken from the "Sessions" table in the O.L.T.P. database. Allows the connection between the "Sessions_History" and "Customers"

tables in the DW. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_sessions_history_insert**” procedure.

- **Trainer_id** – Foreign Key - Identifier taken from the “Sessions” table in the O.L.T.P. database. It allows the connection between the “Sessions_History” and “Trainers” tables in DW. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_sessions_history_insert**” procedure.

- **Location_id** - Foreign Key - Identifier taken from the “Sessions” table in the O.L.T.P. database. It allows the connection between the “Sessions_History” and “Locations” tables in DW. The transfer done using the “**tbdw_sessions_history_insert**” procedure.

- **Customer_Subscription_id** - Foreign Key - Identifier taken from the “Sessions” table from the O.L.T.P. database. Allows the connection between “Sessions_History” and “Subscriptions_History” tables from D.W. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_sessions_history_insert**” procedure.

- **Start_time_id** - The date the client started a training session. Taken from the “Sessions” table. The transfer is done using the “**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**” procedure.

1.5 Identifying the constraints specific to the data warehouses that need to be defined, justifying the choice made

In a Data Warehouse database, primary key or unique constraints can be defined with two additional properties. The first property can be “enable” or “disable”, and the second property can be “validated” or “not validated”.

Using these properties, 4 different results can be obtained.

1. “Enabled Validated” constraint will be used and will ensure that each operation respects that constraint.
2. “Enabled Not Validated” constraint will be used and all new operations will be executed in accordance with it, but existing data will not be verified by it.
3. “Disabled Validated” constraint does not apply to new operations but existing data respects the rules imposed by the constraint
4. “Disabled Not Validated” constraint does not apply to new operations and existing data has not been verified to comply with the rules imposed by the constraint.

For each table in D.W., **Trainers**, **Customers**, **Locations**, **Subscriptions**, **Subscriptions_history**, **Sessions_history**, we will define an **UNIQUE** constraint with the properties “**disable validate**”.

For the **time table** in D.W., “**Time**”, we will apply the “**disable validate**” properties to the primary key “**timp_id**”.

These constraints, defined with the "disable validate" properties, will have the "null" index in the database so that insert, update and delete operations will not be able to be executed on these tables.

We will change the constraints of these properties from “**disable validate**” to “**enable**” when we want to insert new data into the Data Warehouse or when we want to make other types of changes. And we will change them back from “**enable**” to “**disable validate**” when we want to no longer allow these operations to be performed on the tables.

These properties are essential in a Data Warehouse database to ensure data integrity.

At the D.W. level, other primary key constraints and other “unique” keys will be defined. For example, for each table except the “Time” table, there will be the “id” field, defined as “Primary Key”. The default values for this field will be “enable validate noonly”.

1.6 Identifying the data warehouse-specific indexes that need to be defined on the model; formulating a natural language request that will determine the use of the specified indexes and will be implemented in the next stage

1.6.1 Example of BITMAP type index

"Obtain the number of clients expressed as a percentage who have health problems."

In the database, we use the “has_health_issues” column in the “Customers” table to determine whether a customer has health issues or not. If the customer has health issues, they cannot purchase a subscription that does not require the presence of a personal trainer.

In the "has health issues" column we will have the values "0" if the client does not have health issues and the value "1" if he has a health issue.

Since we are talking about a situation where we have low cardinality, we will use a BITMAP index. We will analyze and compare the costs of such a query with and without using the BITMAP index.

1.7 Identifying of the dimension type objects which must be defined on the model

We will define dimension type objects for the “Locations” and “Time” tables in D.W.

For the “Locations” table, the dimension object will contain a hierarchy for the columns (id, city_name, state_name) through which we associate ONE to MANY relationships for it and an attribute for the columns (“address” and “capacity”) through which we associate ONE to ONE relationships between them and the location.

For the “Time” table, the dimension type object will contain two hierarchies. These will be defined for the columns (time_id, week_month, month, quarter, semester, year) through which we associate ONE to MANY relationships for them.

1.8 Identifying the tables to be partitioned and the type of partitioning; formulating a natural language query that will determine their use and will be implemented in the next stage

1.8.1 Example of “Range” partitioning

The goal is to obtain the number of sessions performed per year, over the last 10 years.

A “Range” partitioning will be implemented on the “Sessions_History” table.

1.9 Formulate in natural language of a complex SQL query that will be optimized in the next stage, using techniques specific to warehouse databases. Specification of optimization techniques that could be used for this particular query (advantages / disadvantages of using a particular technique)

This section is reserved for future development. The current version reflects the state of the project at the time of its original academic submission.

1. 10 Formulate in natural language of at least 5 requests, specific to DW, with varying degrees of complexity, embodied in reports (graphics) that will be created in the following stages.

1.10.1 Example 1

1. Check if the capacity of the locations has been exceeded. If it has been exceeded, display the day it was exceeded, the name of the location, the county, and the number of sessions recorded on that day. Sort the results by address, county, date, and capacity. Determine the cost of the query.

2. Modify the previous request to display locations where capacity was exceeded by at least 50%. The data will be sorted by location.

3. For the locations obtained in the previous point, determine if there is an upward trend in the last 5 years of increasing number of sessions. Sort the results by location, year and number of sessions in that year.

1.10.2 Example 2

Display the number of clients who prefer training sessions with male trainers and the number of clients who prefer training sessions with female trainers.

1.10.3 Example 3

Calculate the income for the last 10 years. Display the year and the total amount of income. Sort by year, descending.

2. BACK-END Module

2.1. Creating the O.L.T.P. database and its users

```
create table tb_trainers (trainer_id Int,first_name Varchar2(100),last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50),birth_date Date,gender Varchar2 (25));

create table tb_customers (customer_id Int,first_name Varchar2(100),last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50), date_of_birth Date,gender Varchar2(20), has_health_issues Number(1) default 0);

create table tb_results (result_id int,customer_id int, body_fat Number(3),weight Number(3), Number(3),age int,entry_date Date);

create table tb_customers_subscriptions (customer_subscription_id int,subscription_id int, customer_id int,price Number(6),start_date Date,
end_date Date);

create table tb_subscriptions (subscription_id Number(6),max_number_sessions int, sb_title Varchar2 (256),sb_description Varchar2 (1024),
with_trainer Number(1) default 0,max_number_days int, number(6));

create table tb_sessions (session_id Int,customer_id int,customer_subscription_id Int, location_id Int,trainer_id Int,start_date Date);

create table tb_locations (location_id int,location_capacity int,city_id int,address Varchar2 (256));

create table tb_contracts (contract_id int,trainer_id int,start_date Date,end_date Date, salary Number(10));

create table tb_states (state_id int,state_name Varchar2 (256));

create table tb_cities (city_id int,state_id int,city_name Varchar2 (256));

create table tbe_first_names (first_id int,first_name varchar (100),gender varchar (50));

create table tbe_last_names (last_id int,last_name varchar (100));

create table tbe_health (health_id int,health_value int);
```


I have created the 10 O.L.T.P. database tables, as well as 3 additional tables. The 3 additional tables will be used by the data generation scripts for the O.L.T.P. database tables.

```
alter session set "_ORACLE_SCRIPT"=true;
```

```
create user dwbi_oltp identified by dwbi_oltp_password password expire;
grant create session to dwbi_oltp;
```

```
select username, authentication_type, account_status, expiry_date, created
from dba_users
order by created desc;
```

```
create profile dwbi_oltp_employees limit
cpu_per_call 9000
```

```
sessions_per_user 1  
password_life_time 7  
failed_login_attempts 5;
```

```
alter user dwbi_oltp account unlock;  
alter user dwbi_oltp identified by dwbi_oltp_password;
```

```
alter user dwbi_oltp profile dwbi_oltp_employees;
```

```
select * from dba_profiles where lower(profile) like 'dwbi_%';
```

```
grant select on tb_customers to dwbi_oltp;  
grant select on tb_customers_subscriptions to dwbi_oltp;  
grant select on tb_subscriptions to dwbi_oltp;
```

```
grant insert on tb_customers to dwbi_oltp;  
grant insert on tb_customers_subscriptions to dwbi_oltp;
```

```
grant update on tb_customers to dwbi_oltp;
```

```
SELECT * FROM DBA_TAB_PRIVS where lower(table_name) like 'tb_%';
```

The user “dwbi_oltp” is created with the password “dwbi_oltp_password” and is given “create session” rights.

User profiles are created for O.L.T.P users with CPU consumption per call not exceeding 90 seconds, the right to only one session at a time, the lifetime of a password to be 30 days and the ability to enter the wrong password a maximum of 5 times.

The “dwbi_oltp” user is granted select rights on the “Customers”, “Subscriptions” and “Customers_Subscriptions” tables, insert rights on the “Customers” and “Customers_Subscriptions” tables and update rights on the “Customers” table.

The “dwbi_oltp” user will be used at the front-end application level.

2.2 Generating data and inserting it into the tables

PK autoincrement instructions for OLTP

```
CREATE SEQUENCE tb_trainers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_trainers MODIFY trainer_id int DEFAULT tb_trainers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_customers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_customers MODIFY customer_id int DEFAULT tb_customers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_results_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_results MODIFY result_id int DEFAULT tb_results_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_customers_subscriptions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions MODIFY customer_subscription_id int DEFAULT tb_customers_subscriptions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_subscriptions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_subscriptions MODIFY subscription_id int DEFAULT tb_subscriptions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_sessions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions MODIFY session_id int DEFAULT tb_sessions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_locations_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_locations MODIFY location_id int DEFAULT tb_locations_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_contracts_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_contracts MODIFY contract_id int DEFAULT tb_contracts_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_cities_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_cities MODIFY city_id int DEFAULT tb_cities_seq.nextval NOT NULL;
```


The population of the 3 additional tables. These contain names of people. The data will be used to generate random names for trainers and clients.

```

INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 1, 1);
INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 2, 0);
...
INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 8, 0);
INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 9, 0);

INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 1, 'Oliver', 'male');
INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 2, 'Emma', 'female');
...
INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 39, 'Logan', 'male');
INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 40, 'Nicole', 'female');

INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 1, 'Green');
INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 2, 'Hall');
...
INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 19, 'Morgan');
INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 20, 'Carter');

```


Insert data into the tb_trainers table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_trainers_insert AS

```

t_first_name tb_trainers.first_name%TYPE;
t_last_name tb_trainers.last_name%TYPE;
t_email tb_trainers.email%TYPE;
t_phone_number tb_trainers.phone_number%TYPE;
t_birth_date tb_trainers.birth_date%TYPE;
t_gender tb_trainers.gender%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_rand_choice1 number;
t_rand_choice2 number;
t_last_id tb_trainers.trainer_id%TYPE;

```

```

BEGIN
  t_max_number := 438;
  t_count_number := 1;

  for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
  Loop

  t_rand_choice1 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,40));
  SELECT first_name, gender into t_first_name, t_gender FROM tbe_first_names where first_id = t_rand_choice1;

  t_rand_choice2 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,20));
  SELECT last_name into t_last_name FROM tbe_last_names where last_id = t_rand_choice2;

  t_email := CONCAT(t_first_name, t_last_name);
  t_email := CONCAT(t_email,l_counter);
  t_email := CONCAT(t_email,'@t.dwbi.com');

  t_phone_number := CONCAT(TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)),TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)));
  t_phone_number := CONCAT(t_phone_number,TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1000,9999)));

  SELECT TO_DATE(
    TRUNC(
      DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '1971-01-01','J')
        ,TO_CHAR(DATE '2000-01-01','J')
      )
    ),'J'
  ) into t_birth_date FROM DUAL;
  INSERT INTO tb_trainers
  (
    first_name,
    last_name,
    email,
    phone_number,
    birth_date,
    gender
  )
  VALUES
  (
    t_first_name,
    t_last_name,
    t_email,
    t_phone_number,
    t_birth_date,
    t_gender
  );
  END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_trainers_insert;
end;

```

Connections

- dbwi_project
 - TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS
 - TB_TRAINERS
 - TBOW_CUSTOMERS
 - TBOW_LOCATIONS
 - TBOW_SESSIONS_HISTORY
 - TBOW_SUBSCRIPTIONS
 - TBOW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY
 - TBOW_TIME
 - TBOW_TRAINERS
 - TBOW_TRAINERS
 - TBE_FIRST_NAMES
 - FIRST_ID
 - FIRST_NAME
 - GENDER
 - TBE_HEALTH
 - TBE_LAST_NAMES
 - TRANSACTION_BACKOUT_REPORTS
 - TRANSACTION_BACKOUT_STATES
 - TRANSFORMATIONS
 - TRANSIENT_JOBS

Reports

- All Reports
- Analytic View Reports
- Data Dictionary Reports
- Data Modeler Reports
- OLAP Reports
- TimesTen Reports
- User Defined Reports

Worksheet

```

t_birth_date,
t_gender
);
END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
  tb_trainers_insert;
end;

```

Script Output

Task completed in 0.184 seconds

1 row inserted.

Procedure TB_TRAINERS_INSERT compiled

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Doms Output

Buffer Size: 20000

dbwi_project

Connections

- Oracle Connections
 - dbwi_project
 - Tables (Filtered)
 - Views
 - Indexes
 - Packages
 - Procedures
 - Functions
 - Operators
 - Queues
 - Queue Tables
 - Triggers
 - Types
 - Sequences
 - Materialized Views
 - Materialized View Logs
 - Synonyms
 - Public Synonyms
 - Database Links

Reports

- All Reports
- Analytic View Reports
- Data Dictionary Reports
- Data Modeler Reports
- OLAP Reports
- TimesTen Reports
- User Defined Reports

Worksheet

```
select * from tb_trainers order by trainer_id desc;
```

Query Result

Fetches 20 rows in 0.017 seconds

TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST NAME	EMAIL	PHONE NUMBER	BIRTH DATE	GENDER
1	Lydia	Bates	LydiaBates438@t.dwb1.com	1646485165	17-NOV-80	female
2	Ryan	Green	RyanGreen437@t.dwb1.com	3217194227	28-NOV-96	male
3	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes436@t.dwb1.com	5567697233	24-NOV-72	male
4	Hannah	Bates	HannahBates435@t.dwb1.com	3827499419	01-AUG-84	female
5	Julia	Palmer	JuliaPalmer434@t.dwb1.com	7103692916	21-APR-75	female
6	Elaine	Brooks	ElaineBrooks433@t.dwb1.com	2179821244	08-JUN-92	female
7	Elaine	Hughes	ElaineHughes432@t.dwb1.com	3644255049	11-MAY-73	female
8	Louis	Holmes	LouisHolmes431@t.dwb1.com	2242239332	11-SEP-77	male
9	Charles	Cooper	CharlesCooper430@t.dwb1.com	8117552651	06-NOV-99	male
10	Vivian	Andrews	VivianAndrews429@t.dwb1.com	5305323821	07-SEP-97	female
11	Hannah	Ross	HannahRoss428@t.dwb1.com	4549964990	15-MAR-90	female
12	Logan	Clarke	LoganClarke427@t.dwb1.com	6445982255	29-APR-81	male
13	Amanda	Shepard	AmandaShepard426@t.dwb1.com	9371863563	13-AUG-95	female
14	Louis	Stevens	LouisStevens425@t.dwb1.com	8377578513	05-APR-80	male
15	Alice	Shepard	AliceShepard424@t.dwb1.com	6271273661	26-MAY-76	female
16	Heleen	Stevens	HeleenStevens423@t.dwb1.com	7799049475	06-APR-84	female
17	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes422@t.dwb1.com	2858469512	27-JUL-98	male
18	Oscar	Brooks	OscarBrooks421@t.dwb1.com	9165062439	23-OCT-72	male
19	Elizabeth	Hopkins	ElizabethHopkins420@t.dwb1.com	9033546619	28-JAN-85	female
20	Victoria	Ross	VictoriaRoss419@t.dwb1.com	8166634380	16-NOV-86	female

Doms Output

Buffer Size: 20000

Messages - Log

Messages | Logging Page | Statements

Insert data into the tb_customers table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_customers_insert AS

```

t_first_name tb_customers.first_name%TYPE;
t_last_name tb_customers.last_name%TYPE;
t_email tb_customers.email%TYPE;
t_phone_number tb_customers.phone_number%TYPE;
t_date_of_birth tb_customers.date_of_birth%TYPE;
t_gender tb_customers.gender%TYPE;
t_has_health_issues tb_customers.has_health_issues%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_rand_choice1 number;
t_rand_choice2 number;
t_rand_choice3 number;

```

BEGIN

```
t_max_number := 3872;
```

```

t_count_number := 1;

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

t_rand_choice1 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,40));
SELECT first_name, gender into t_first_name, t_gender FROM tbe_first_names where first_id = t_rand_choice1;

t_rand_choice2 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,20));
SELECT last_name into t_last_name FROM tbe_last_names where last_id = t_rand_choice2;

t_email := CONCAT(t_first_name, t_last_name);
t_email := CONCAT(t_email,l_counter);
t_email := CONCAT(t_email,'@c.dwbi.com');

t_phone_number := CONCAT(TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)),TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)));
t_phone_number := CONCAT(t_phone_number,TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1000,9999)));

SELECT TO_DATE(
TRUNC(
DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '1961-01-01','J')
,TO_CHAR(DATE '2012-01-01','J')
)
),'J'
) into t_date_of_birth FROM DUAL;

t_rand_choice3 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,9));
SELECT health_value into t_has_health_issues FROM tbe_health where health_id = t_rand_choice3;

INSERT INTO tb_customers
(
first_name,
last_name,
email,
phone_number ,
date_of_birth,
gender,
has_health_issues
)
VALUES
(
t_first_name,
t_last_name,
t_email,
t_phone_number,
t_date_of_birth,
t_gender,
t_has_health_issues
);
END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_customers_insert;
end;

```


Insert data into the tb_subscriptions table

insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (1,'1 Intrare Spa', 'În saloanele de spa din zilele noastre primesti tratamente de îngrijire faciala si corporala, diverse tipuri de masaj, sauna, aromoterapie, cromoterapie, terapie prin pietre, dusuri, împachetari cu plante, bai în piscina, tratamente anticelulitice si antivergeturi',1,1,60);

insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (1,'1 Intrare piscina copii', 'Oferta valabila pentru copii cu varstele cuprinse între 10-16 ani',1,1,30);

insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (1,'1 Intrare Sala Fitness', 'Oferta include acces la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutate pentru a antrena fiecare zona de musculatura corpului ',0,1,35);

...

insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (12,'Pachet lunar fitness cu antrenor', 'Oferta include 12 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate într-un interval de 31 de zile. Antrenamentul se desfasoara cu antrenor',1,31,720);


```

FROM tb_subscriptions
ORDER BY DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE
FETCH FIRST ROW ONLY;
end if;

t_customer_id := t_rand_choice1;
t_subscription_id := t_rand_choice2;

SELECT price into t_price from tb_subscriptions where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;
SELECT max_number_days into t_duration from tb_subscriptions where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;

t_duration := t_duration - 1;

SELECT TO_DATE(
TRUNC(
DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '2000-01-01','J')
,TO_CHAR(DATE '2023-02-12','J')
)
),'J'
) into t_start_date FROM DUAL;

t_end_date := t_start_date + t_duration;

--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_subscription_id:' || t_subscription_id);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_customer_id:' || t_customer_id);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_start_date:' || t_start_date);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_end_date:' || t_end_date);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_price:' || t_price);

INSERT INTO tb_customers_subscriptions
(
subscription_id,
customer_id,
start_date,
end_date,
price
)
VALUES
(
t_subscription_id,
t_customer_id,
t_start_date,
t_end_date,
t_price
);

-- DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_required_trainer:' || t_required_trainer);
-- DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_subscription_id:' || t_subscription_id);

END Loop;
END;
/
set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_customers_subscriptions_insert;
end;

```


Insert data into the tb_states and tb_cities tables

```

insert into tb_states values (1,'Alba');
insert into tb_states values (2,'Arad');
...
insert into tb_states values (41,'Valcea');
insert into tb_states values (42,'Vrancea');

insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (1,'Alba Iulia');
insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (1,'Sebes');
...
insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (42,'Jaristea');
insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (42,'Ploscuteni');

```


Insert data into the tb_locations table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_locations_insert AS

```

t_location_capacity tb_locations.location_capacity%TYPE;
t_city_id tb_locations.city_id%TYPE;
t_address tb_locations.address%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_rand_choice number;
t_rand_choice2 number;

```

BEGIN

```

t_max_number := 70;
t_count_number := 1;

```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number

Loop

```
t_location_capacity := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(50,100));

t_rand_choice2 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,840));
SELECT city_id into t_city_id FROM tb_cities where city_id = t_rand_choice2;

t_rand_choice := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(10000,100000));
t_address := CONCAT('address',t_rand_choice);

INSERT INTO tb_locations
(
    location_capacity,
    city_id,
    address
)
VALUES
(
    t_location_capacity,
    t_city_id,
    t_address
);
END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_locations_insert;
end;
```


Insert data into the tb_contracts table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_contracts_insert AS

```
t_trainer_id tb_contracts.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_start_date tb_contracts.start_date%TYPE;
t_end_date tb_contracts.end_date%TYPE;
t_salary tb_contracts.salary%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_rand_choice1 number;
t_rand_choice2 number;
t_duration number;
```

BEGIN

```
select count(*) into t_max_number from tb_trainers;
t_count_number := 1;
```

```
for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop
```

```
t_trainer_id := l_counter;
```

```
t_rand_choice1 := Trunc(dbms_random.value(15,45));
t_rand_choice2 := t_rand_choice1 * 100;
t_salary := t_rand_choice2;
```

```
SELECT TO_DATE(
  TRUNC(
    DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '2000-01-01','J')
      ,TO_CHAR(DATE '2023-02-12','J'))
  ),'J'
) into t_start_date FROM DUAL;
```

```
t_end_date := add_months(t_start_date, trunc(DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(1,72)));
```

```
INSERT INTO tb_contracts
(
  trainer_id,
  start_date,
  end_date,
  salary
)
```

```
VALUES
(
  t_trainer_id,
  t_start_date,
  t_end_date,
  t_salary
);
END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_contracts_insert;
end;
```


Insert data into the tb_sessions table

```
CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_sessions_insert AS
```

```

t_customer_id tb_sessions.customer_id%TYPE;
t_customer_subscription_id tb_sessions.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
t_location_id tb_sessions.location_id%TYPE;
t_trainer_id tb_sessions.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_start_date tb_sessions.start_date%TYPE;
t_max_number_sessions tb_subscriptions.max_number_sessions%TYPE;
t_unique_customer_subscription_id tb_sessions.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_rand_number_sessions number;
t_sessions_counter number;
t_required_trainer tb_customers.has_health_issues%type;

```

```
BEGIN
```

```

    BEGIN

```

```

        SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_count_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by customer_subscription_id asc;

```

```

        SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_max_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by customer_subscription_id desc;

```

```

    EXCEPTION

```

```

        WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN

```

```

            t_count_number := 0;

```

```

            t_max_number := 0;

```

```

        END;

```

```

t_transfers := 0;

```

```

t_non_unique_records_found := 0;

```

```

dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Subscriptions in the OLTP.');
```

```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number

```

```

Loop

```

```

    t_customer_subscription_id := l_counter;

```

```

    BEGIN

```

```

        select max_number_sessions into t_max_number_sessions from tb_subscriptions tb1, tb_customers_subscriptions tb2
        where tb1.subscription_id = tb2.subscription_id and tb2.customer_subscription_id = l_counter;

```

```

EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_max_number_sessions := null;
  END;

if t_max_number_sessions = 1 then
  BEGIN
    select customer_subscription_id into t_unique_customer_subscription_id from tb_sessions where customer_subscription_id =
t_customer_subscription_id;
  EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_unique_customer_subscription_id := null;
  END;

  IF t_unique_customer_subscription_id is null THEN

    select customer_id, start_date
    into t_customer_id, t_start_date
    from tb_customers_subscriptions
    where customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;

    select has_health_issues into t_required_trainer from tb_customers where customer_id = t_customer_id;

    if t_required_trainer = 1 then
      t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,438));
    else
      t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(0,438));
      if t_trainer_id = 0 then
        t_trainer_id := null;
      end if;
    end if;

    t_location_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,70));

    INSERT INTO tb_sessions
    (
      customer_id,
      customer_subscription_id,
      location_id,
      trainer_id,
      start_date
    )
    VALUES
    (
      t_customer_id,
      t_customer_subscription_id,
      t_location_id,
      t_trainer_id,
      t_start_date
    );
    t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
  END IF;
  t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

if t_max_number_sessions > 1 then

  t_rand_number_sessions := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,t_max_number_sessions));
  t_sessions_counter := 0;

  for l_counter2 in t_sessions_counter..t_rand_number_sessions
  Loop

    select customer_id, start_date
    into t_customer_id, t_start_date

```

```

from tb_customers_subscriptions
where customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;

select has_health_issues into t_required_trainer from tb_customers where customer_id = t_customer_id;

if t_required_trainer = 1 then
t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,438));
else
t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(0,438));
if t_trainer_id = 0 then
t_trainer_id := null;
end if;
end if;

t_location_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,70));

INSERT INTO tb_sessions
(
customer_id,
customer_subscription_id,
location_id,
trainer_id,
start_date
)
VALUES
(
t_customer_id,
t_customer_subscription_id,
t_location_id,
t_trainer_id,
t_start_date
);
t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;

end loop;

end if;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Sessions added. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;
/

set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_sessions_insert;
end;
```

Connections

Worksheet

```

IF t_unique_customer_subscription_id is null THEN
    select customer_id, start_date
    into t_customer_id, t_start_date
    from tb_customers_subscriptions
    where customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;

    select has_health_issues into t_required_trainer from tb_customers where customer_id = t_customer_id;

    if t_required_trainer = 1 then

```

Script Output

Task completed in 142.073 seconds

15000 Subscriptions in the OLTP.
765797 Sessions added.
3197 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Dims Output

Buffer Size:20000

15000 Subscriptions in the OLTP.
765797 Sessions added.
3197 Non unique records found.

Messages | Logging Page | Statements | Compiler

Connections

Worksheet

```

select * from tb_sessions order by session_id desc;

```

Query Result

Fetches 50 rows in 0.007 seconds

SESSION_ID	CUSTOMER_ID	CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID	LOCATION_ID	TRAINER_ID	START_DATE
1	765797	1021	15000	15	334 23-SEP-02
2	765796	1021	15000	54	234 23-SEP-02
3	765795	1021	15000	43	239 23-SEP-02
4	765794	1021	15000	26	23 23-SEP-02
5	765793	1021	15000	40	247 23-SEP-02
6	765792	1021	15000	15	313 23-SEP-02
7	765791	1021	15000	39	360 23-SEP-02
8	765790	1021	15000	5	247 23-SEP-02
9	765789	1021	15000	38	231 23-SEP-02
10	765788	1021	15000	65	353 23-SEP-02
11	765787	1021	15000	47	202 23-SEP-02
12	765786	1021	15000	15	292 23-SEP-02
13	765785	1021	15000	17	246 23-SEP-02
14	765784	1021	15000	47	126 23-SEP-02
15	765783	1021	15000	56	211 23-SEP-02
16	765782	1021	15000	66	425 23-SEP-02
17	765781	1021	15000	23	51 23-SEP-02
18	765780	1021	15000	43	240 23-SEP-02
19	765779	1021	15000	11	402 23-SEP-02
20	765778	1021	15000	17	313 23-SEP-02

Dims Output

Buffer Size:20000

Messages | Logging Page | Statements

Display count(*) for the 10 tables in OLTP

```

select 'tb_trainers' Table_name, count(*) "COUNT" from tb_trainers
union all
select 'tb_customers', count(*) from tb_customers
union all
select 'tb_subscriptions', count(*) from tb_subscriptions
union all
select 'tb_customers_subscriptions', count(*) from tb_customers_subscriptions
union all
select 'tb_states', count(*) from tb_states
union all
select 'tb_cities', count(*) from tb_cities
union all
select 'tb_locations', count(*) from tb_locations

```

```

union all
select 'tb_contracts', count(*) from tb_contracts
union all
select 'tb_sessions', count(*) from tb_sessions
union all
select 'tb_results', count(*) from tb_results;

```

The screenshot shows a database management tool interface. The main window displays a SQL query in a query builder:


```

union all
select 'tb_customers_suscriptions', count(*) from tb_customers_suscriptions
union all
select 'tb_states', count(*) from tb_states
union all
select 'tb_cities', count(*) from tb_cities
union all
select 'tb_locations', count(*) from tb_locations
union all
select 'tb_contracts', count(*) from tb_contracts
union all
select 'tb_sessions', count(*) from tb_sessions
union all
select 'tb_results', count(*) from tb_results;

```

 Below the query, the 'Query Result' pane shows a table with 10 rows and 2 columns: 'TABLE_NAME' and 'COUNT'. The data is as follows:

TABLE_NAME	COUNT
1 tb_trainers	438
2 tb_customers	3872
3 tb_subscriptions	20
4 tb_customers_suscriptions	15000
5 tb_states	42
6 tb_cities	840
7 tb_locations	70
8 tb_contracts	438
9 tb_sessions	765797
10 tb_results	0

 The interface also includes a 'Connections' pane on the left, a 'Reports' pane, and a 'Doms Output' pane at the bottom showing execution details like 'All Rows Fetched: 10 in 0.041 seconds' and '15000 Subscriptions in the OLTP. 765797 Sessions added. 3157 Non-unique records found.'

2.3 Creating the D.W. database and its users

```

create table tbdw_trainers (id int, trainer_id Int, first_name Varchar2(100), last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50), birth_date Date, hire_date Date, contract_end_date Date, gender Varchar2 (25));

create table tbdw_customers (id int, customer_id Int, first_name Varchar2(100), last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50), date_of_birth Date, gender Varchar2(20),
has_health_issues Number(1) default 0);

create table tbdw_subscriptions_history (id int, subscription_id int, customer_subscription_id int, customer_id int, start_time_id date,
end_time_id date, price number(6));

create table tbdw_subscriptions ( id int, subscription_id int, max_number_sessions int, title varchar2 (256),
description Varchar2 (1024), with_trainer int, max_number_days int );

create table tbdw_sessions_history ( id int, session_id int, customer_id int, trainer_id int, location_id int, customer_subscription_id int,
start_time_id date );

create table tbdw_locations ( id int, location_id int, capacity int, state_name varchar2 (256), city_name varchar2 (256), address varchar2 (256),
city_id int, state_id int );

create table tbdw_time (timp_id date, an int, semestru int, trimestru int, luna int, saptamana_an int, saptamana_luna int, zi_an int,
zi_luna int, zi_saptamana int, zi_nume varchar(100), luna_nume varchar(100), weekend int, an_bisect int,
saptamana_calendar int, saptamana_an_business int);

```

Worksheet Query Builder

```

203 si_saptamana int,
204 si_nume varchar(100),
205 luna_nume varchar(100),
206 weekend int,
207 an_bisect int,
208 saptamana_calendar int,
209 saptamana_an_business int
210 );
211

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.128 seconds

Table TBW_TRAINERS created.

Table TBW_CUSTOMERS created.

Table TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY created.

Table TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS created.

Table TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY created.

Table TBW_LOCATIONS created.

Table TBW_TIME created.

Doms Output

Buffer Size:20000

dwbi_project x

Click on an identifier with the Control key down to perform "Go to Declaration"

| Line 210 Column 4 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

Worksheet Query Builder

```

205 luna_nume varchar(100),
206 weekend int,
207 an_bisect int,
208 saptamana_calendar int,
209 saptamana_an_business int
210 );
211
212 select table_name from user_tables where table_name like 'TBW%';
213

```

Script Output x Query Result x

All Rows Fetched: 7 in 0.072 seconds

TABLE_NAME
1 TBW_CUSTOMERS
2 TBW_LOCATIONS
3 TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY
4 TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS
5 TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY
6 TBW_TIME
7 TBW_TRAINERS

Doms Output

Buffer Size:20000

dwbi_project x

Click on an identifier with the Control key down to perform "Go to Declaration"

| Line 212 Column 66 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

alter session set "_ORACLE_SCRIPT"=true;

create user dwbi_dw identified by dwbi_dw_password password expire;
grant create session to dwbi_dw;

create profile dwbi_dw_employees limit
cpu_per_call 90000
sessions_per_user 1
password_life_time 7
failed_login_attempts 3;

alter user dwbi_dw profile dwbi_dw_employees;

select * from dba_profiles where lower(profile) like 'dwbi_%';

```
alter user dwbi_dw account unlock;
alter user dwbi_dw identified by dwbi_dw_password;
```

```
select username, authentication_type, account_status, expiry_date, created
from dba_users
order by created desc;
```

```
grant select on tbdw_customers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_trainers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_locations to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_time to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_subscriptions to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_subscriptions_history to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_sessions_history to dwbi_dw;
```

```
grant select on tb_customers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_trainers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_results to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_contracts to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_cities to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_states to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_locations to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_sessions to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_customers_subscriptions to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_subscriptions to dwbi_dw;
```

```
SELECT * FROM DBA_TAB_PRIVS where lower(table_name) like 'tb_%';
```

The user “dwbi_dw” is created with the password “dwbi_dw_password” and given the right “create session”.

User profiles are created for D.W. users with CPU consumption per call not exceeding 900 seconds, with the right to only one session at a time, the lifetime of a password to be 30 days, and the ability to enter the wrong password for a maximum of 3 times.

The user "dwbi_dw" receives select rights on all tables in the O.L.T.P and D.W.

2.4 Populating the D.W. database with information using data from the OLTP database as a source

PK autoincrement instructions for D.W.

```

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_trainers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_trainers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_customers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_customers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_subscriptions_history_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_subscriptions_history_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_subscriptions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_subscriptions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_sessions_history_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_sessions_history_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_locations_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_locations_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

```


Data transfer for the tbdw_trainers table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_trainers_insert AS

```

t_trainer_id tbdw_trainers.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_first_name tbdw_trainers.first_name%TYPE;
t_last_name tbdw_trainers.last_name%TYPE;
t_email tbdw_trainers.email%TYPE;
t_phone_number tbdw_trainers.phone_number%TYPE;
t_date_of_birth tbdw_trainers.birth_date%TYPE;
t_gender tbdw_trainers.gender%TYPE;
t_hire_date tbdw_trainers.hire_date%TYPE;
t_contract_end_date tbdw_trainers.contract_end_date%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_unique_email tbdw_customers.email%TYPE;
t_unique_trainer_id tbdw_customers.customer_id%TYPE;
t_non_unique_records_found number;

BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT trainer_id into t_count_number FROM tb_trainers where rownum = 1 order by trainer_id asc;
    SELECT trainer_id into t_max_number FROM tb_trainers where rownum = 1 order by trainer_id desc;
  EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_count_number := 0;
      t_max_number := 0;
  END;

  t_transfers := 0;
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Trainers in the OLTP.');
```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

```

  t_trainer_id := 0;
  t_unique_email := null;
  t_unique_trainer_id := null;
  BEGIN
    select trainer_id into t_trainer_id from tb_trainers where trainer_id = l_counter;
  EXCEPTION
```

```

WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_trainer_id := 0;
END;

IF t_trainer_id > 0 THEN

    BEGIN
        select trainer_id,email into t_unique_trainer_id,t_unique_email from tbdw_trainers where trainer_id = t_trainer_id;
    EXCEPTION
        WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
            t_unique_email := null;
            t_unique_trainer_id := null;
        END;
    IF t_unique_trainer_id is null and t_unique_email is null THEN

        select tb1.trainer_id, tb1.first_name, tb1.last_name, tb1.email, tb1.phone_number, tb1.birth_date, tb1.gender , tb2.start_date,
        tb2.end_date
        into t_trainer_id, t_first_name, t_last_name, t_email, t_phone_number, t_date_of_birth, t_gender, t_hire_date,
        t_contract_end_date
        from tb_trainers tb1, tb_contracts tb2
        where tb1.trainer_id = tb2.trainer_id
        and tb1.trainer_id = t_trainer_id;

        INSERT INTO tbdw_trainers
        (
            trainer_id,
            first_name,
            last_name,
            email,
            phone_number,
            birth_date,
            hire_date,
            contract_end_date,
            gender
        )
        VALUES
        (
            t_trainer_id,
            t_first_name,
            t_last_name,
            t_email,
            t_phone_number,
            t_date_of_birth,
            t_hire_date,
            t_contract_end_date,
            t_gender
        );

        t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
    ELSE
        t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
    END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Trainers transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_trainers_insert;

```

end;

```
END Loop;
dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Trainers transferred. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_trainers_insert;
end;
```

Procedure tbdw_trainers_insert compiled

438 Trainers in the OLTP.
438 Trainers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Doms Output

438 Trainers in the OLTP.
438 Trainers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

```
select * from tbdw_trainers order by id desc;
```

ID	TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	HIRE_DATE	CONTRACT_END_DATE	GENDER
1	438	Lydia	Bates	LydiaBates438@t.dwb1.com	1646485165	17-NOV-80	27-OCT-16	27-OCT-19	female
2	437	Ryan	Green	RyanGreen437@t.dwb1.com	3217194227	28-NOV-96	17-JUN-07	17-MAR-09	male
3	436	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes436@t.dwb1.com	5567697233	24-NOV-72	01-AUG-16	01-JAN-18	male
4	435	Hannah	Bates	HannahBates435@t.dwb1.com	3827490419	01-AUG-84	12-SEP-22	12-DEC-22	female
5	434	Julia	Palmer	JuliaPalmer434@t.dwb1.com	7103692916	21-APR-75	09-SEP-09	09-JAN-12	female
6	433	Elaine	Brooks	ElaineBrooks433@t.dwb1.com	2179821244	08-JUN-92	14-MAY-22	14-APR-28	female
7	432	Elaine	Hughes	ElaineHughes432@t.dwb1.com	3644255049	11-MAY-73	23-JUN-17	23-JUL-22	female
8	431	Louis	Holmes	LouisHolmes431@t.dwb1.com	2242239332	11-SEP-77	02-SEP-10	02-OCT-10	male
9	430	Charles	Cooper	CharlesCooper430@t.dwb1.com	8117552651	06-NOV-99	07-FEB-23	07-AUG-26	male
10	429	Vivian	Andrews	VivianAndrews429@t.dwb1.com	5305232821	07-SEP-97	19-SEP-08	19-FEB-09	female
11	428	Hannah	Rose	HannahRose428@t.dwb1.com	4549964990	15-MAR-80	09-DEC-05	09-APR-10	female
12	427	Logan	Clarke	LoganClarke427@t.dwb1.com	4445902255	29-APR-81	01-JUL-19	01-JAN-20	male
13	426	Amanda	Shepard	AmandaShepard426@t.dwb1.com	9371843563	13-AUG-95	04-OCT-02	04-DEC-03	female
14	425	Louis	Stevens	LouisStevens425@t.dwb1.com	8377578513	05-APR-80	19-DEC-15	19-SEP-19	male
15	424	Alice	Shepard	AliceShepard424@t.dwb1.com	6271273661	26-MAY-76	26-JUL-05	26-JAN-08	female
16	423	Helen	Stevens	HelenStevens423@t.dwb1.com	7799049475	06-APR-84	28-OCT-20	28-JAN-21	female
17	422	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes422@t.dwb1.com	2850469512	27-JUL-99	06-SEP-15	06-MAY-20	male
18	421	Oscar	Brooks	OscarBrooks421@t.dwb1.com	9165002439	23-OCT-72	12-AUG-05	12-MAY-08	male
19	420	Elizabeth	Hopkins	ElizabethHopkins420@t.dwb1.com	9033544619	28-JAN-85	09-SEP-05	09-JAN-07	female
20	419	Amelia	Stevens	AmeliaStevens419@t.dwb1.com	0122243350	16-JUN-65	06-MAR-11	06-MAR-15	female

Data transfer for the tbdw_customers table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_customers_insert AS

```
t_customer_id tbdw_customers.customer_id%TYPE;
t_first_name tbdw_customers.first_name%TYPE;
t_last_name tbdw_customers.last_name%TYPE;
t_email tbdw_customers.email%TYPE;
t_phone_number tbdw_customers.phone_number%TYPE;
t_date_of_birth tbdw_customers.date_of_birth%TYPE;
t_gender tbdw_customers.gender%TYPE;
t_has_health_issues tbdw_customers.has_health_issues%TYPE;
```

```

t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_unique_email tbdw_customers.email%TYPE;
t_unique_customer_id tbdw_customers.customer_id%TYPE;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT customer_id into t_count_number FROM tb_customers where rownum = 1 order by customer_id asc;
    SELECT customer_id into t_max_number FROM tb_customers where rownum = 1 order by customer_id desc;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_count_number := 0;
    t_max_number := 0;
  END;

  t_transfers := 0;
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Customers in the OLTP.');
```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

```

  t_customer_id := 0;
  t_unique_email := null;
  t_unique_customer_id := null;

  select customer_id into t_customer_id from tb_customers where customer_id = l_counter;

  IF t_customer_id > 0 THEN

    BEGIN
      select customer_id,email into t_unique_customer_id,t_unique_email from tbdw_customers where customer_id = t_customer_id;
    EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_unique_email := null;
      t_unique_customer_id := null;
    END;
    IF t_unique_customer_id is null and t_unique_email is null THEN

      select customer_id,first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, date_of_birth, gender, has_health_issues
      into t_customer_id, t_first_name, t_last_name, t_email, t_phone_number, t_date_of_birth, t_gender, t_has_health_issues
      from tb_customers
      where customer_id = t_customer_id;

      INSERT INTO tbdw_customers
      (
        customer_id,
        first_name,
        last_name,
        email,
        phone_number ,
        date_of_birth,
        gender,
        has_health_issues
      )
      VALUES
      (
        t_customer_id,
        t_first_name,
        t_last_name,
        t_email,
        t_phone_number,
        t_date_of_birth,
        t_gender,
```

```

        t_has_health_issues
    );

    t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
    t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Customers transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_customers_insert;
end;

```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window shows a PL/SQL procedure named 'tbdw_customers_insert' being executed. The code in the Worksheet pane is as follows:

```

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Customers transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_customers_insert;
end;

```

The Script Output pane indicates that the task completed in 1.003 seconds. The Doms Output pane shows the following results:

```

3872 Customers in the OLTP.
3872 Customers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

```

The Connections pane on the left shows a tree view of database objects, including tables like TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TBOW_CUSTOMERS, TBOW_LOCATIONS, TBOW_SESSIONS_HISTORY, TBOW_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TBOW_TIME, TBOW_TRAINERS, TBE_FIRST_NAMES, TBE_HEALTH, TBE_LAST_NAMES, and TRANSACTION_BACKOUT_REPORTS. The Reports pane at the bottom left shows various report categories like All Reports, Analytic View Reports, Data Dictionary Reports, Data Modeler Reports, OLAP Reports, TimesTen Reports, and User Defined Reports.

Data transfer for the tblw_subscriptions table

```
CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tblw_subscriptions_insert AS
```

```

t_subscription_id tblw_subscriptions.subscription_id%TYPE;
t_max_number_sessions tblw_subscriptions.max_number_sessions%TYPE;
t_max_number_days tblw_subscriptions.max_number_days%TYPE;
t_title tblw_subscriptions.title%TYPE;
t_description tblw_subscriptions.description%TYPE;
t_with_trainer tblw_subscriptions.with_trainer%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_subscription_id tblw_subscriptions.subscription_id%TYPE;

```

```
BEGIN
```

```
  BEGIN
```

```
    SELECT subscription_id into t_count_number FROM tb_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by subscription_id asc;
```

```
    SELECT subscription_id into t_max_number FROM tb_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by subscription_id desc;
```

```
  EXCEPTION
```

```
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
```

```
      t_count_number := 0;
```

```
      t_max_number := 0;
```

```
  END;
```

```
  t_transfers := 0;
```

```
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
```

```
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Subscriptions in the OLTP.');
```

```
  for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
```

```
  Loop
```

```
    t_subscription_id := 0;
```

```
  BEGIN
```

```
    select subscription_id into t_subscription_id from tb_subscriptions where subscription_id = l_counter;
```

```
  EXCEPTION
```

```
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
```

```
      t_subscription_id := 0;
```

```

END;

IF t_subscription_id > 0 THEN

BEGIN
    select subscription_id into t_unique_subscription_id from tbdw_subscriptions where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;
EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
        t_unique_subscription_id := null;
END;

IF t_unique_subscription_id is null THEN

    select subscription_id, max_number_sessions, sb_title, sb_description, with_trainer, max_number_days
    into t_subscription_id, t_max_number_sessions, t_title, t_description, t_with_trainer, t_max_number_days
    from tb_subscriptions
    where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;

    INSERT INTO tbdw_subscriptions
    (
        subscription_id,
        max_number_sessions,
        title,
        description,
        with_trainer,
        max_number_days
    )
    VALUES
    (
        t_subscription_id,
        t_max_number_sessions,
        t_title,
        t_description,
        t_with_trainer,
        t_max_number_sessions
    );

    t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
    t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Subscriptions transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_subscriptions_insert;
end;

```

```

END Loop;
dms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Subscriptions transferred.');
```

```

dms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found.');
```

END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_subscriptions_insert;
end;

Task completed in 0.064 seconds

Procedure TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_INSERT compiled

20 Subscriptions in the OLTP.
20 Subscriptions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Dms Output

0 Non unique records found.
20 Subscriptions in the OLTP.
20 Subscriptions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

```

select * from tbdw_subscriptions order by id desc;
```

ID	SUBSCRIPTI...	MAX_NUMBER_SESSIONS	TITLE	DESCRIPTION
1	20	20	16 Pachet 2 luni fitness cu antrenor	Oferta include 16 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 60 de z...
2	19	19	12 Pachet lunar fitness cu antrenor	Oferta include 12 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 31 de z...
3	18	18	8 Pachet lunar fitness cu antrenor	Oferta include 8 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 31 de zi...
4	17	17	11 Intrare Sala Fitness cu Antrenor	Oferta include acces la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea pentru a ant...
5	16	16	365 Abonament anual aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 1 an la programul de aerobic
6	15	15	180 Abonament demi aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 6 luni la programul de aerobic
7	14	14	90 Abonament quarter aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 3 luni la programul de aerobic
8	13	13	31 Abonament lunar sedinte aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 1 luna la programul de aerobic
9	12	12	365 Abonament anual piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 1 an la piscina
10	11	11	180 Abonament demi piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 6 luni la piscina
11	10	10	90 Abonament quarter piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 3 luni la piscina
12	9	9	31 Abonament lunar piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 31 de zile la piscina
13	8	8	365 Abonament anual fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 1 an la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea pentru
14	7	7	180 Abonament demi fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 6 luni de zile la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greuta
15	6	6	90 Abonament quarter fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 3 luni de zile la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greuta
16	5	5	31 Abonament lunar fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 31 de zile la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea p
17	4	4	8 Abonament lunar sedinte aerobic	Oferta include 8 intrari la programul de aerobic ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 31 de zi...
18	3	3	11 Intrare Sala Fitness	Oferta include acces la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea pentru a ant...
19	2	2	11 Intrare piscina copii	Oferta valabila pentru copii cu varstele cuprinse intre 10-16 ani

Data transfer for the tbdw_locations table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_locations_insert AS

```

t_location_id tbdw_locations.location_id%TYPE;
t_capacity tbdw_locations.capacity%TYPE;
t_state_name tbdw_locations.state_name%TYPE;
t_city_name tbdw_locations.city_name%TYPE;
t_address tbdw_locations.address%TYPE;
t_city_id tbdw_locations.city_id%TYPE;
t_state_id tbdw_locations.state_id%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_location_id tbdw_locations.location_id%TYPE;
```

```

BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT location_id into t_count_number FROM tb_locations where rownum = 1 order by location_id asc;
    SELECT location_id into t_max_number FROM tb_locations where rownum = 1 order by location_id desc;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_count_number := 0;
    t_max_number := 0;
  END;

  t_transfers := 0;
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Locations in the OLTP.');
```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

```

  t_location_id := 0;

  BEGIN
    select location_id into t_location_id from tb_locations where location_id = l_counter;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_location_id := 0;
  END;

  IF t_location_id > 0 THEN

    BEGIN
      select location_id into t_unique_location_id from tbdw_locations where location_id = t_location_id;
    EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_unique_location_id := null;
    END;
    IF t_unique_location_id is null THEN

      select tb1.location_id, tb1.location_capacity, tb3.state_name, tb2.city_name, tb1.address, tb1.city_id, tb2.state_id
      into t_location_id, t_capacity, t_state_name, t_city_name, t_address, t_city_id, t_state_id
      from tb_locations tb1, tb_cities tb2, tb_states tb3
      where tb1.location_id = t_location_id and tb1.city_id = tb2.city_id and tb2.state_id = tb3.state_id;

      INSERT INTO tbdw_locations
      (
        location_id,
        capacity,
        state_name,
        city_name,
        address,
        city_id,
        state_id
      )
      VALUES
      (
        t_location_id,
        t_capacity,
        t_state_name,
        t_city_name,
        t_address,
        t_city_id,
        t_state_id
      );

      t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
    ELSE
      t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
    
```

```
END IF;
```

```
END IF;
```

```
END Loop;
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Locations transferred.');
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found.');
```

```
END;
```

```
set serveroutput on;
```

```
begin
```

```
tbdw_locations_insert;
```

```
end;
```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window shows a PL/SQL script in the Worksheet area, which is the same code provided in the text above. The Script Output window shows the execution results: "Task completed in 0.077 seconds", "Procedure TBDW_LOCATIONS_INSERT compiled", "70 Locations in the OLTP.", "70 Locations transferred.", and "0 Non unique records found.". The Dims Output window shows "0 Non unique records found." and "70 Locations in the OLTP. 70 Locations transferred. 0 Non unique records found.". The Compiler - Log window is empty. The Connections pane on the left shows a tree view of database objects, including TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TBOW_CUSTOMERS, TBOW_LOCATIONS, TBOW_SESSIONS_HISTORY, TBOW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY, TBOW_TIME, TBOW_TRAINERS, TBE_FIRST_NAMES, TBE_HEALTH, TBE_LAST_NAMES, and TRANSACTION_BACKOUT_REPORTS. The Reports pane at the bottom left shows a list of report categories like Analytic View Reports, Data Dictionary Reports, etc.

Data Transfer for the `tblw_time` table

```
CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tblw_time_insert AS
```

```

t_max_date date;
t_min_date date;
l_counter date;
l_variable_interval varchar(2);
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_timp_id tblw_time.timp_id%TYPE;

```

```
BEGIN
```

```

SELECT to_date('01-JAN-1964') into t_min_date FROM dual;
SELECT to_date('31-DEC-1964') + interval '24' hour into t_max_date FROM dual;

```

```

dbms_output.put_line (to_char(t_min_date,'YYYY-MON-DD HH24:MI') || ' Is the start date. ');
dbms_output.put_line (to_char(t_max_date,'YYYY-MON-DD HH24:MI') || ' Is the end date. ');

```

```

t_transfers := 0;
t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
l_counter := t_min_date;

```

```
BEGIN
```

```

while l_counter <= t_max_date
LOOP

```

```

    l_variable_interval := to_char(l_counter,'HH24');
    --dbms_output.put_line (to_char(l_counter,'YYYY-MON-DD HH24:MI') || ' Is the current date in loop. and ' || cast(l_variable_interval as integer) || ' is current hour' );

```

```
BEGIN
```

```

    select timp_id into t_unique_timp_id from tblw_time where timp_id = l_counter and rownum = 1;

```

```
EXCEPTION
```

```

    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN

```

```

        t_unique_timp_id := to_date('01-JAN-1100');

```

```
END;
```

```

IF t_unique_timp_id = to_date('01-JAN-1100') then

```

```

insert into tbdw_time
select
  data timp_id,
  extract(year from data) an,
  case when extract(month from data) < 7 then 1 else 2 end semestru,
  TO_CHAR(data, 'q') trimestru,
  extract(month from data) luna,
  to_char(data,'WW') SAPTAMANA_AN,
  to_char(data,'W')SAPTAMANA_LUNA,
  to_char(data,'DDD') ZI_AN,
  to_char(data,'DD') ZI_LUNA,
  to_char(data,'D') ZI_SAPTAMANA,
  to_char(data,'DAY') ZI_NUME,
  to_char(data,'MONTH') LUNA_NUME,
  case when to_char(data,'D') not in (1,7) then 0 else 1 end WEEKEND,
  case when mod(extract(year from data), 4) = 0 and mod(extract(year from data), 4) <> 100 then 1 else 0 end AN_BISECT,
  to_number(to_char(data,'IW')) SAPTAMANA_CALENDAR,
  case when to_number(to_char(data,'D')) <> 1 then to_number(to_char(data,'IW')) - 1
    else to_number(to_char(data,'IW')) end SAPTAMANA_AN_BUSINESS
from(
  select to_date(l_counter) + cast(l_variable_interval as integer)/24 as data from dual);

  t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
  t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

  l_counter := l_counter + interval '1' hour;
END Loop;
END;
dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Records transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');

END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_time_insert;
end;

```


The data entered into the “Time” table was generated by running the procedure for 10-year intervals of days. For each day of the year, the procedure will insert 24 entries, for the 24 hours of the day. The date and time are stored in the variable “timp_id”.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a query result for the table `tbdw_subscriptions_history`. The query is: `select saptamana_an, saptamana_luna, zi_an, zi_luna, zi_saptamana, zi_nume, luna_nume, weekend, an, bisect, saptamana_calendar, saptamana_an_business from tbdw_time order by timp_id desc;`

The query result shows 19 rows of data for the year 2024. The columns are: `TO_CHAR(TIMP_ID, 'YYYY-MM-DDHH24:MM')`, `AN`, `SEMESTRU`, `TRIMESTRU`, `LLUNA`, `SAPTAMANA_LUNA`, `SAPTAMANA_AN`, `ZI_LUNA`, `ZI_SAPTAMANA`, `ZI_NUME`, `LLUNA_NUME`, `WEEKEND`, `AN_BISECT`, and `SAPTA`.

TO_CHAR(TIMP_ID, 'YYYY-MM-DDHH24:MM')	AN	SEMESTRU	TRIMESTRU	LLUNA	SAPTAMANA_LUNA	SAPTAMANA_AN	ZI_LUNA	ZI_SAPTAMANA	ZI_NUME	LLUNA_NUME	WEEKEND	AN_BISECT	SAPTA
2025-01-01 00:00	2025	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	0
2024-12-31 23:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
3 2024-12-31 22:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
4 2024-12-31 21:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
5 2024-12-31 20:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
6 2024-12-31 19:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
7 2024-12-31 18:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
8 2024-12-31 17:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
9 2024-12-31 16:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
10 2024-12-31 15:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
11 2024-12-31 14:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
12 2024-12-31 13:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
13 2024-12-31 12:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
14 2024-12-31 11:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
15 2024-12-31 10:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
16 2024-12-31 09:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
17 2024-12-31 08:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
18 2024-12-31 07:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
19 2024-12-31 06:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1

Data transfer the tbdw_subscriptions_history table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert AS

```
t_subscription_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.subscription_id%TYPE;
t_customer_subscription_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
t_customer_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.customer_id%TYPE;
t_start_time_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.start_time_id%TYPE;
t_end_time_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.end_time_id%TYPE;
t_price tbdw_subscriptions_history.price%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_customer_subscription_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
```

BEGIN

BEGIN

SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_count_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by customer_subscription_id asc;

SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_max_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by customer_subscription_id desc;

EXCEPTION

WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN

t_count_number := 0;

t_max_number := 0;

END;

t_transfers := 0;

t_non_unique_records_found := 0;

dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Locations in the OLTP.');

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number

Loop

t_customer_subscription_id := 0;

BEGIN

```

select customer_subscription_id into t_customer_subscription_id from tb_customers_subscriptions where customer_subscription_id =
l_counter;
EXCEPTION
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
t_customer_subscription_id := 0;
END;

IF t_customer_subscription_id > 0 THEN

BEGIN
select customer_subscription_id into t_unique_customer_subscription_id from tbdw_subscriptions_history where
customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;
EXCEPTION
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
t_unique_customer_subscription_id := null;
END;

IF t_unique_customer_subscription_id is null THEN

select subscription_id, customer_id, start_date, end_date, price
into t_subscription_id, t_customer_id, t_start_time_id, t_end_time_id, t_price
from tb_customers_subscriptions
where customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;

INSERT INTO tbdw_subscriptions_history
(
subscription_id,
customer_subscription_id,
customer_id,
start_time_id,
end_time_id,
price
)
VALUES
(
t_subscription_id,
t_customer_subscription_id,
t_customer_id,
t_start_time_id,
t_end_time_id,
t_price
);

t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Subscriptions transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert;
end;

```

Procedure `TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_INSERT` compiled

15000 Locations in the OLTP.
15000 Subscriptions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Task completed in 3.457 seconds

15000 Locations in the OLTP.
15000 Locations transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

1964-JAN-01 00:00 Is the start date.

select * from tbdw_subscriptions_history order by id desc;

ID	SUBSCRIPTION_ID	CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID	CUSTOMER_ID	START_TIME_ID	END_TIME_ID	PRICE
1	15000	15	15000	1021 23-SEP-02	21-MAR-03	1245
2	14959	5	14959	1013 30-JUL-16	29-AUG-16	230
3	14998	18	14998	1039 13-JUL-04	12-AUG-04	520
4	14997	17	14997	591 01-DEC-05	01-DEC-05	70
5	14996	12	14996	2409 10-SEP-19	08-SEP-20	2040
6	14995	14	14995	178 21-MAR-16	18-JUN-16	685
7	14994	12	14994	1696 17-FEB-07	16-FEB-08	2040
8	14993	18	14993	3318 23-SEP-13	23-OCT-13	520
9	14992	14	14992	1262 11-NOV-11	05-FEB-12	685
10	14991	18	14991	600 04-DEC-22	03-JAN-23	520
11	14990	10	14990	1506 24-JUL-00	21-OCT-00	670
12	14989	9	14989	2457 14-DEC-13	13-JAN-14	300
13	14988	19	14988	118 13-JUL-22	12-AUG-22	720
14	14987	17	14987	2361 18-DEC-06	18-DEC-06	70
15	14986	17	14986	212 30-JUN-17	30-JUN-17	70
16	14985	7	14985	3422 07-OCT-19	03-APR-20	960
17	14984	5	14984	3719 17-APR-18	17-MAY-18	230
18	14983	1	14983	3316 26-JUL-15	26-JUL-15	60
19	14982	2	14982	525 09-NOV-20	09-NOV-20	30
20	14981	14	14981	2333 10-SEP-13	08-SEP-13	2040

Data transfer for the `tbdw_sessions_history` table

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE `tbdw_sessions_history_insert` AS

```

t_session_id tbdw_sessions_history.session_id%TYPE;
t_customer_id tbdw_sessions_history.customer_id%TYPE;
t_trainer_id tbdw_sessions_history.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_location_id tbdw_sessions_history.location_id%TYPE;
t_customer_subscription_id tbdw_sessions_history.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
t_start_time tbdw_sessions_history.start_time_id%TYPE;

```

```

t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_session_id tbdw_sessions_history.session_id%TYPE;
BEGIN
BEGIN
SELECT session_id into t_count_number FROM tb_sessions where rownum = 1 order by session_id asc;
SELECT session_id into t_max_number FROM tb_sessions where rownum = 1 order by session_id desc;
EXCEPTION
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
t_count_number := 0;
t_max_number := 0;
END;

t_transfers := 0;
t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Records in the OLTP.');
```

```

-- t_count_number := 800001;
-- t_max_number := 900000;

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

BEGIN
select session_id into t_session_id from tb_sessions where session_id = l_counter;
EXCEPTION
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
t_session_id := 0;
END;

IF t_session_id > 0 THEN

BEGIN
select session_id into t_unique_session_id from tbdw_sessions_history where session_id = t_session_id;
EXCEPTION
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
t_unique_session_id := null;
END;

IF t_unique_session_id is null THEN

select customer_id, customer_subscription_id, location_id, trainer_id, start_date
into t_customer_id, t_customer_subscription_id, t_location_id, t_trainer_id, t_start_time
from tb_sessions
where session_id = t_session_id;

INSERT INTO tbdw_sessions_history
(
session_id,
customer_id,
trainer_id,
location_id,
customer_subscription_id,
start_time_id
)
VALUES
(
t_session_id,
t_customer_id,
t_trainer_id,
t_location_id,
t_customer_subscription_id,
t_start_time

```

```

);

t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Sessions transferred. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;
/

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_sessions_history_insert;
end;

```


Procedure TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY_INSERT compiled

```

765797 Records in the OLTP.
165797 Sessions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

```

Doms Output

```

dwb_project x
0 Non unique records found.

765797 Records in the OLTP.
100000 Sessions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

765797 Records in the OLTP.

```

Query Result 1 x

```

select * from tblw_sessions_history order by id desc;

```

Fetches 50 rows in 0.009 seconds

ID	SESSION_ID	CUSTOMER_ID	TRAINER_ID	LOCATION_ID	CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID	START_TIME_ID
1	765797	765797	1021	334	15	15000 23-SEP-02
2	765796	765796	1021	234	54	15000 23-SEP-02
3	765795	765795	1021	239	43	15000 23-SEP-02
4	765794	765794	1021	23	26	15000 23-SEP-02
5	765793	765793	1021	247	40	15000 23-SEP-02
6	765792	765792	1021	313	15	15000 23-SEP-02
7	765791	765791	1021	368	39	15000 23-SEP-02
8	765790	765790	1021	247	5	15000 23-SEP-02
9	765789	765789	1021	231	38	15000 23-SEP-02
10	765788	765788	1021	353	65	15000 23-SEP-02
11	765787	765787	1021	202	47	15000 23-SEP-02
12	765786	765786	1021	292	15	15000 23-SEP-02
13	765785	765785	1021	246	17	15000 23-SEP-02
14	765784	765784	1021	126	47	15000 23-SEP-02
15	765783	765783	1021	211	56	15000 23-SEP-02
16	765782	765782	1021	425	66	15000 23-SEP-02
17	765781	765781	1021	51	23	15000 23-SEP-02
18	765780	765780	1021	240	43	15000 23-SEP-02
19	765779	765779	1021	402	11	15000 23-SEP-02
20	765778	765778	1021	316	17	15000 23-SEP-02

Display count(*) for all D.W. tables

```

select 'tbdw_trainers' Table_name, count(*) "COUNT" from tbdw_trainers
union all
select 'tbdw_customers', count(*) from tbdw_customers
union all
select 'tbdw_subscriptions', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions
union all
select 'tbdw_locatons', count(*) from tbdw_locatons
union all
select 'tbdw_time', count(*) from tbdw_time
union all
select 'tbdw_subscriptions_history', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions_history
union all

```

```
select 'tbdw_sessions_history', count(*) from tbdw_sessions_history;
```

The screenshot shows a database management tool interface. The main window displays a SQL query in the Query Builder:

```
union all  
select 'tbdw_customers', count(*) from tbdw_customers  
union all  
select 'tbdw_subscriptions', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions  
union all  
select 'tbdw_locations', count(*) from tbdw_locations  
union all  
select 'tbdw_time', count(*) from tbdw_time  
union all  
select 'tbdw_subscriptions_history', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions_history  
union all  
select 'tbdw_sessions_history', count(*) from tbdw_sessions_history;
```

The Query Result pane shows the following table:

TABLE_NAME	COUNT
1 tbdw_trainers	438
2 tbdw_customers	3872
3 tbdw_subscriptions	20
4 tbdw_locations	70
5 tbdw_time	534745
6 tbdw_subscriptions_history	15000
7 tbdw_sessions_history	765797

The Dims Output pane shows the following text:

```
0 Non unique records found.  
765797 Records in the OLTP.  
100000 Sessions transferred.  
0 Non unique records found.  
765797 Records in the OLTP.
```

2.5 Defining the constraints

Primary Key Constraints for OLTP

```
ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (trainer_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (customer_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_results ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_results_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (result_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (customer_subscription_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (subscription_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (session_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_locations_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (location_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_contracts ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_contracts_pk PRIMARY KEY (contract_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_states ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_states_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (state_id));  
ALTER TABLE tb_cities ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_cities_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (city_id));
```


Foreign Key Constraints for OLTP

```
ALTER TABLE tb_results ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_results_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id) REFERENCES tb_customers(customer_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_subscriptions_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id)
REFERENCES tb_customers(customer_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_subscriptions_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (subscription_id)
REFERENCES tb_subscriptions(subscription_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_customer_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_subscription_id)
REFERENCES tb_customers_subscriptions(customer_subscription_id);
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_traier_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (trainer_id) REFERENCES tb_trainers(trainer_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id)
REFERENCES tb_customers(customer_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_location_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (location_id) REFERENCES tb_locations(location_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_locations_city_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (city_id) REFERENCES tb_cities(city_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_contracts ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_contracts_trainer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (trainer_id) REFERENCES tb_trainers(trainer_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_cities ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_cities_state_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (state_id) REFERENCES tb_states(state_id) );
```

```
80 REFERENCES tb_trainers(trainer_id)
81 );
82
83 ALTER TABLE tb_cities
84 ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_cities_state_id_fk
85 FOREIGN KEY (state_id)
86 REFERENCES tb_states(state_id)
87 );
88
```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.201 seconds.

Table TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS altered.

Table TB_SESSIONS altered.

Table TB_SESSIONS altered.

Table TB_SESSIONS altered.

Table TB_SESSIONS altered.

Table TB_LOCATIONS altered.

Table TB_CONTRACTS altered.

Table TB_CITIES altered.

```
26 and cons.constraint_name = cols.constraint_name
27 and cons.owner = 'SYS'
28 and cons.table_name like 'TB%'
29 ORDER BY cols.table_name, cols.position;
30
31 ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
32
33 ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
34
```

Script Output x Query Result x

All Rows Fetched: 9 in 0.201 seconds

CONSTRAINT_NAME	CONSTRAINT_TYPE	TABLE_NAME	R_CONSTRAINT_NAME	STATUS
1 TB_CITIES_STATE_ID_FK	R	TB_CITIES	TB_STATES_ID_FK	ENABLED
2 TB_CONTRACTS_TRAINER_ID_FK	R	TB_CONTRACTS	TB_TRAINERS_ID_FK	ENABLED
3 TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS_SUBSCRIPTION_ID_FK	R	TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS	TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS_ID_FK	ENABLED
4 TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS_CUSTOMER_ID_FK	R	TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS	TB_CUSTOMERS_ID_FK	ENABLED
5 TB_LOCATIONS_CITY_ID_FK	R	TB_LOCATIONS	TB_CITIES_ID_FK	ENABLED
6 TB_RESULTS_CUSTOMER_ID_FK	R	TB_RESULTS	TB_CUSTOMERS_ID_FK	ENABLED
7 TB_SESSIONS_LOCATION_ID_FK	R	TB_SESSIONS	TB_LOCATIONS_ID_FK	ENABLED
8 TB_SESSIONS_CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID_FK	R	TB_SESSIONS	TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS_ID_FK	ENABLED
9 TB_SESSIONS_TRAINER_ID_FK	R	TB_SESSIONS	TB_TRAINERS_ID_FK	ENABLED

Dims Output

Buffer Size:20000

UNIQUE constraints for OLTP

```
ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
```

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Connections:** A tree view on the left showing various database schemas like TSQS, TTS_ERRORS, TYPE_MISC\$, etc.
- Worksheet:** A query editor window containing the following SQL code:

```
27 AND cons.owner = 'SYS'  
28 AND cons.table_name like 'TB%'  
29 ORDER BY cons.table_name, cols.position;  
30  
31 ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);  
32  
33 ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);  
34  
35
```
- Script Output:** A window showing the execution results:

```
Table TB_SESSIONS altered.  
Table TB_LOCATIONS altered.  
Table TB_CONTRACTS altered.  
Table TB_STATES altered.  
Table TB_CITIES altered.  
Table TB_TRAINERS altered.  
Table TB_CUSTOMERS altered.
```
- DBMS Output:** A window at the bottom showing the execution status: "Task completed in 0.089 seconds".

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Worksheet:** A query editor window containing the following SQL code:

```
23 select cons.constraint_name, cons.constraint_type, cons.table_name, cons.status  
24 from all_constraints cons, all_cons_columns cols  
25 where cons.constraint_type = 'U'  
26 AND cons.constraint_name = cols.constraint_name  
27 AND cons.owner = 'SYS'  
28 AND cons.table_name like 'TB%'  
29 ORDER BY cons.table_name, cols.position;  
30  
31 ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
```
- Script Output:** A window showing the execution results:

```
All Rows Fetched: 2 in 0.251 seconds  
CONSTRAINT_NAME | CONSTRAINT_TYPE | TABLE_NAME | STATUS  
1 TB_CUSTOMERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL U | TB_CUSTOMERS | ENABLED  
2 TB_TRAINERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL U | TB_TRAINERS | ENABLED
```
- DBMS Output:** A window at the bottom showing the execution status: "All Rows Fetched: 2 in 0.251 seconds".

Click on an identifier with the Control key down to perform "Go to Declaration"

Line 29 Column 41 | Insert | Modified | Windows: O

Primary Key constraints for DW

```
ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_trainers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_customers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_locations_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_time ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_time_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (time_id));
```

The screenshot displays the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Connections:** A tree view on the left showing a project named 'dwb_project' with various schema objects like TSQ\$, TTS_ERROR\$, TYPE_MISC\$, etc.
- Worksheet:** The main area contains a 'Query Builder' window with the following SQL script:

```
220 ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
221  
222 ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
223  
224 ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_locations_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
225  
226 ALTER TABLE tbdw_time ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_time_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (time_id));  
227  
228
```
- Script Output:** Below the worksheet, a 'Script Output' window shows the execution results:

```
Task completed in 0.195 seconds  
Table TBW_TRAINERS altered.  
Table TBW_CUSTOMERS altered.  
Table TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY altered.  
Table TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS altered.  
Table TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY altered.  
Table TBW_LOCATIONS altered.  
Table TBW_TIME altered.
```
- Reports:** A 'Reports' window on the left lists various report types like 'Analytic View Reports', 'Data Dictionary Reports', etc.
- Bottom Panel:** A 'Doms Output' window at the bottom shows the current project 'dwb_project'.

The screenshot shows a database management tool interface. The main window displays a SQL query in the 'Worksheet' tab. The query is as follows:

```

24 AND cons.constraint_name = cols.constraint_name
25 AND cons.owner = 'SYS'
26 AND cons.table_name like 'TBDW%'
27 ORDER BY cols.table_name, cols.position;
28
29 ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
30
31 ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
32
33
34

```

The 'Query Result' tab shows the following table:

CONSTRAINT_NAME	CONSTRAINT_TYPE	TABLE_NAME	R_CONSTRAINT_NAME	STATUS
TBDW_CUSTOMERS_ID_PK	P	TBDW_CUSTOMERS	(null)	ENABLED
TBDW_LOCATIONS_ID_PK	P	TBDW_LOCATIONS	(null)	ENABLED
TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY_ID_PK	P	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	(null)	ENABLED
TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_ID_PK	P	TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS	(null)	ENABLED
TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_ID_PK	P	TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY	(null)	ENABLED
TBDW_TIME_ID_PK	P	TBDW_TIME	(null)	ENABLED
TBDW_TRAINERS_ID_PK	P	TBDW_TRAINERS	(null)	ENABLED

Foreign Key Constraints for DW

```

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_customers(customer_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_trainer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (trainer_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_trainers(trainer_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_location_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (location_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_locations(location_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_customer_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY
(customer_subscription_id) REFERENCES tbdw_subscriptions_history(customer_subscription_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD (CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (subscription_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_subscriptions(subscription_id));

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD (CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_customers(customer_id));

```



```
ALTER TABLE tdw_sessions_history ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_unique_session_id UNIQUE (session_id) disable validate;
```

```
ALTER TABLE tdw_subscriptions ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_unique_subscription_id UNIQUE (subscription_id) disable validate;
```

```
ALTER TABLE tdw_time modify CONSTRAINT tbdw_time_id_pk disable validate;
```


For each table, **tdw_trainers**, **tdw_customers**, **tdw_locations**, **tdw_subscriptions**, **tdw_subscriptions_history**, **tdw_sessions_history**, we have defined a UNIQUE constraint with the properties “**disable validate**”. After these constraints have been implemented the insert, update and delete operations on these tables will not be able to be executed.

Also, for the **tbdw_time** table, the primary key "**time_id**" was modified and the "**disable validate**" properties were assigned to it so that the 3 operations will not be able to be executed on it either.

To add new data to the Data Warehouse, I will modify the constraint of the table I want to update by assigning it the "**enable**" property. I apply these changes to the fact table "**tbdw_subscriptions_history**".

alter table **tbdw_subscriptions_history** modify constraint tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id **enable**;

I added 100 new entries to the OLTP database for the **tb_customers_subscriptions** table. It now contains 15,100 records, and the **tbdw_subscriptions_history** table contains 15,000 records.

```
select 'tb_customers_subscriptions' Table_name, count(*) "COUNT" from tb_customers_subscriptions
union all
select 'tbdw_subscriptions_history', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions_history;
```


We run the data transfer procedure “**tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert**” and notice that the 100 new records have been transferred from the O.L.T.P to the D.W.

After the update, the two databases have the same number of records, both having 15100.

To lock the `tbdw_subscriptions_history` table again, I will modify the constraint `"tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id"` and reassign the properties `"disable validate"` to it.

alter table `tbdw_subscriptions_history` modify constraint `tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id` `disable validate`;

I will try to delete data from this table, namely the record with id 15100.

I confirm that this record exists.

```
select * from tblw_subscriptions_history where id = 15100;
```


And I execute the deletion of this record.

I notice that the data deletion was not executed and I received the following error message “ORA-25128 No insert/update/delete on table with constraint (SYS.TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_UNIQUE_CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID) disabled and validated”.

2.6 Definition of indexes and SQL queries accompanied by their execution plan (which shows that the optimizer effectively uses the defined indexes)

2.6.1 BITMAP type index

I will use a **BITMAP index** to determine the percentage of customers who have a health problem. We will analyze and compare the costs of such a query with and without the use of a **Bitmap index**.

First, I analyze the costs without using the index.

```
create table tbdw_customers_temp as select * from tbdw_customers;
```

```
Analyze table tbdw_customers_temp compute statistics;
```

```
select max_number_customers,
       round(max_number_customers / (select count(*) from tbdw_customers_temp) * 100,2) as
percentage
from (select count(*) max_number_customers
```

```

from tbdw_customers_temp
where has_health_issues = 1);

```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a query in the Query Builder:

```

from user_tables
where lower(table_name) in (lower('tbdw_customers_temp'),lower('tbdw_customers')));

Analyze table tbdw_customers_temp compute statistics:

select max_number_customers,
       round(max_number_customers / (select count(*) from tbdw_customers_temp) * 100,2) as percentage
from (select count(*) max_number_customers
      from tbdw_customers_temp
      where has_health_issues = 1);

select table_name, tablespace_name, num_rows, Blocks, Empty_Blocks, last_analyzed

```

Below the query, the Explain Plan is shown with the following table:

OPERATION	OBJECT_NAME	OPTIONS	CARDINALITY	COST
SELECT STATEMENT			1	28
SORT		AGGREGATE	1	1
TABLE ACCESS	TBDW_CUSTOMERS_TEMP	FULL	3872	14
VIEW			1	14
SORT		AGGREGATE	1	1
TABLE ACCESS	TBDW_CUSTOMERS_TEMP	FULL	1936	14
Filter Predicates				
Other XML				
HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES=1				
(info)				
info type="has_user_tab"				

The total cost of the query is 28.

I notice the total cost of this query as “28”.

I create a BITMAP type index.

```

alter table tbdw_customers_temp add constraint tbdw_customers_temp_pk Primary Key (id) enable
novalidate;

```

```

CREATE BITMAP INDEX ind_bmp_tbdw_customers_has_health_issues_test_temp
ON tbdw_customers_temp(has_health_issues);

```

```

ANALYZE INDEX ind_bmp_tbdw_customers_has_health_issues_test_temp COMPUTE STATISTICS;

```

explain plan

```

set statement_id = 's1_tbdw_customers_bmp_temp'

```

for

```

select max_number_customers,
       round(max_number_customers / (select count(*) from tbdw_customers_temp) * 100,2) as
percentage
from (select count(*) max_number_customers
      from tbdw_customers_temp
      where has_health_issues = 1);

```

```

SELECT plan_table_output

```

```

FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 's1_tbdw_customers_bmp_temp','serial'));

```


Plan hash value: 4120872880

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		1	13	2 (0)	00:00:01
1	SORT AGGREGATE		1			
2	BITMAP CONVERSION TO ROWIDS		3872		1 (0)	00:00:01
3	BITMAP INDEX FAST FULL SCAN	IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP				
4	VIEW		1	13	1 (0)	00:00:01
5	SORT AGGREGATE		1	2		
6	BITMAP CONVERSION COUNT		1936	3872	1 (0)	00:00:01
* 7	BITMAP INDEX FAST FULL SCAN	IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP				

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

7 - filter("HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES"=1)

After using the **BITMAP** index, we see the total cost of this query becoming “13”.

2.7 Defining dimension type objects, validating them (proving that the data complies with the constraints imposed by these types of objects)

2.7.1 Dimension object for the “LOCATIONS” table

CREATE DIMENSION tbdw_dim_locations

LEVEL locatie IS (tbdw_locations.id)

LEVEL oras IS (tbdw_locations.city_name)

LEVEL judet IS (tbdw_locations.state_name)

HIERARCHY h1

(

locatie CHILD OF

oras CHILD OF

judet)

ATTRIBUTE locatie DETERMINES (tbdw_locations.address, tbdw_locations.capacity);

Executing the validation of the dimension object for the “Locations” table.

```
execute dbms_dimension.validate_dimension(upper('tbdw_dim_locations'),false,true,'st_tbdw_dim_locations');
```


I check if the data in the “Locations” table meets the constraints imposed by the defined dimension object.

```
SELECT * FROM dimension_exceptions WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_locations';
```



```
SELECT * FROM tbdw_locations
WHERE rowid IN (SELECT bad_rowid
FROM dimension_exceptions
WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_locations');
```


I notice that the entered data meets the constraints imposed by the dimension object.

2.7.2 The dimension object for the “TIME” table.

CREATE DIMENSION tbdw_dim_time

```
LEVEL zi IS (tbdw_time.timp_id)
LEVEL saptamana IS (tbdw_time.saptamana_luna)
LEVEL luna IS (tbdw_time.luna)
LEVEL trimestru IS (tbdw_time.trimestru)
LEVEL semestru IS (tbdw_time.semestru)
LEVEL an IS (tbdw_time.an)
```

HIERARCHY h1

```
(
  zi CHILD OF
  saptamana CHILD OF
  luna CHILD OF
  an
)
```

HIERARCHY h2

```
(
  zi CHILD OF
  luna CHILD OF
  trimestru CHILD OF
  semestru CHILD OF
  an);
```


Executing the script to validate the dimension object for the “Time” table.

```
execute dbms_dimension.validate_dimension(upper('tbw_dim_time'),false,true,'st_tbdw_dim_time');
```


I checked whether the data in the “Time” table meets the constraints imposed by the defined dimension object.

```
SELECT * FROM dimension_exceptions WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_time';
```



```
SELECT * FROM tbdw_time
WHERE rowid IN (SELECT bad_rowid
FROM dimension_exceptions
WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_time');
```


I notice that the data in the "TIME" table does not respect the constraints imposed by the defined dimension object.

2.8 Defining partitions; defining SQL queries accompanied by their execution plan, which shows that the optimizer uses partitions efficiently

2.8.1 “Range” partition example

Defining the partition.

```
CREATE TABLE tbdw_sessions_partition_last_decade
PARTITION BY RANGE(start_time_id)
(
PARTITION sessions_2015
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2015','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2016
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2016','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2017
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2017','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2018
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2018','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2019
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2019','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2020
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2020','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2021
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2021','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2022
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2022','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2023
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2023','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2024
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2024','DD/MM/YYYY')))
AS
SELECT *
FROM tbdw_sessions_history
WHERE start_time_id >= TO_DATE('01/01/2015','DD/MM/YYYY')
AND start_time_id < TO_DATE('31/12/2024','DD/MM/YYYY');
```


I check the cost of the query without using the partition.

```

EXPLAIN PLAN
SET STATEMENT_ID = 'st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp'
FOR
select tb2.an, count(tb1.id) from tbdw_sessions_history tb1, tbdw_time tb2
where tb2.an < 2025
AND tb2.an > 2014
AND tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
group by tb2.an
order by tb2.an asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table','st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp','serial'));

```

```

EXPLAIN PLAN
SET STATEMENT_ID = 'st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp'
FOR
select tb2.an, count(tb1.id) from tbdw_sessions_history tb1, tbdw_time tb2
where tb2.an < 2025
AND tb2.an > 2014
AND tb1.start_time_id = tb2.time_id
group by tb2.an
order by tb2.an asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan table','st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp','serial'));

```

PLAN_HASH_VALUE: 1277050673

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		10	330	2625 (4)	00:00:01
1	SORT GROUP BY		10	330	2625 (4)	00:00:01
* 2	HASH JOIN		6984	225K	2623 (4)	00:00:01
3	VIEW	VW_GBF_7	6984	143K	1160 (7)	00:00:01
4	HASH GROUP BY		6984	55872	1160 (7)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	765K	5982K	1108 (2)	00:00:01
* 6	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_TIME	87805	1028K	1462 (1)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

```

2 - access("ITEM_1"="TB2"."TIMP_ID")
6 - filter("TB2"."AN">2014 AND "TB2"."AN"<2025)

```

Plan hash value: 1277050673

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		10	330	2625 (4)	00:00:01
1	SORT GROUP BY		10	330	2625 (4)	00:00:01
* 2	HASH JOIN		6984	225K	2623 (4)	00:00:01
3	VIEW	VW_GBF_7	6984	143K	1160 (7)	00:00:01
4	HASH GROUP BY		6984	55872	1160 (7)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	765K	5982K	1108 (2)	00:00:01
* 6	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_TIME	87805	1028K	1462 (1)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

```

2 - access("ITEM_1"="TB2"."TIMP_ID")
6 - filter("TB2"."AN">2014 AND "TB2"."AN"<2025)

```

I check the query cost using the partition.

```

EXPLAIN PLAN
SET STATEMENT_ID = 'st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_part_temp'
FOR
select tb2.an, count(tb1.id) from tbdw_sessions_partition_last_decade tb1, tbdw_time tb2
where tb2.an < 2025
AND tb2.an > 2014
AND tb1.start_time_id = tb2.time_id
group by tb2.an
order by tb2.an asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan table','st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_part_temp','serial'));

```


Plan hash value: 2629054689

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time	Pstart	Pstop
0	SELECT STATEMENT		10	320	1882 (3)	00:00:01		
1	SORT GROUP BY		10	320	1882 (3)	00:00:01		
* 2	HASH JOIN		2449	78368	1881 (2)	00:00:01		
3	VIEW	VW_GBF_7	2449	48980	418 (6)	00:00:01		
4	HASH GROUP BY		2449	17143	418 (6)	00:00:01		
5	PARTITION RANGE ALL		273K	1873K	400 (2)	00:00:01	1	10
6	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_PARTITION_LAST_DECADE	273K	1873K	400 (2)	00:00:01	1	10
* 7	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_TIME	87805	1028K	1462 (1)	00:00:01		

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

```

2 - access("ITEM_1"="TB2"."TIMP_ID")
7 - filter("TB2"."AN">2014 AND "TB2"."AN"<2025)

```

It can be seen that using the partition decreased the cost from 2625 to 1882.

2.9 SQL query optimization proposed in the analysis stage

2.9.1 the execution plan chosen by the cost-based optimizer (explanation of steps taken)

This section is reserved for future development. The current version reflects the state of the project at the time of its original academic submission.

2.9.2 suggestions for optimizing the request, specifying the execution plan obtained

This section is reserved for future development. The current version reflects the state of the project at the time of its original academic submission.

2.10 Creating reports of varying complexity (at this level there will be SQL scripts, without graphical representation)

2.10.1 Example 1

Check if the capacity of the locations has been exceeded. If it has been exceeded, display the day it was exceeded, the name of the location, the county, and the number of sessions recorded on that day. Sort the results by address, county, date, and capacity. Determine the cost of the query.

I check the capacity of the locations.

```
select id, address, capacity from tbdw_locations order by capacity asc;
```


The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, the 'Connections' pane is open, showing a tree view of database objects under 'DW_PROJECT3.1'. The 'Tables (Filtered)' folder is expanded, listing various tables including TB_CITIES, TB_CONTRACTS, TB_CUSTOMERS, TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_LOCATIONS, TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TBW_CUSTOMERS, TBW_LOCATIONS, TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY, TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY, TBW_TIME, TBW_TRAINERS, TBE_FIRST_NAMES, TBE_HEALTH, and TBE_LAST_NAMES. The main window displays a 'Query Builder' with the following SQL query:

```
1 select id, address, capacity from tbdw_locations order by capacity asc;
```

Below the query, the 'Query Result' pane shows the output of the query. It indicates that all 70 rows were fetched in 0.047 seconds. The results are displayed in a table with three columns: ID, ADDRESS, and CAPACITY.

ID	ADDRESS	CAPACITY
1	23 address81564	50
2	67 address33794	50
3	5 address45313	53
4	35 address95923	54
5	63 address53055	54
6	14 address48345	54
7	27 address80609	54
8	29 address78826	54
9	47 address34486	55
10	16 address81038	55
11	4 address75448	55
12	53 address84834	56
13	15 address22078	57

I notice that the locations have a fairly high capacity. I am reducing the capacity of the locations to demonstrate the functionality of the scripts.

```
update tbdw_locations set capacity = capacity - 40;
```

I run the script for the request.

```

Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.address,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity;

```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The Query Builder window contains the following SQL query:

```

1 Select
2   tb2.start_time_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
3 From
4   tbdw_sessions_history tb2
5 JOIN
6   tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
7 Group By
8   tb1.address,
9   tb1.state_name,
10  tb2.start_time_id,
11  tb1.capacity
12 Having
13   count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity;
14

```

The Query Result window shows the following data:

START_TIME_ID	ADDRESS	STATE_NAME	NUMBER_OF_SESSIONS	CAPACITY
132 28-MAR-16	address01564	Neamt	11	10
133 17-OCT-09	address01564	Neamt	11	10
134 07-MAY-17	address01564	Neamt	11	10
135 13-OCT-15	address01564	Neamt	12	10
136 19-FEB-08	address33794	Constanta	11	10
137 06-NOV-22	address33794	Constanta	20	10
138 03-MAY-03	address34486	Dolj	16	15
139 30-OCT-22	address33794	Constanta	11	10
140 31-JUL-08	address78826	Prahova	15	14
141 07-JUN-00	address01564	Neamt	11	10
142 27-JUL-08	address33794	Constanta	11	10
143 07-FEB-23	address33794	Constanta	11	10

I'm checking the cost.

```

explain plan
set statement_id = 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_1'
for
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id

```

Group By

tb1.address,
tb1.state_name,
tb2.start_time_id,
tb1.capacity

Having

count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity;

SELECT plan_table_output

FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_1', 'serial'));

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a query in the Worksheet:

```
12 tb1.state_name,  
13 tb2.start_time_id,  
14 tb1.capacity  
15 Having  
16 count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity;  
17  
18 SELECT plan_table_output  
19 FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_1', 'serial'));
```

Below the query, the Explain Plan window shows the execution plan for the query:

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		621K	182M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 1	FILTER					
2	HASH GROUP BY		621K	182M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 3	HASH JOIN		621K	182M	1114 (2)	00:00:01
4	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_LOCATIONS	70	20020	3 (0)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	621K	13M	1106 (2)	00:00:01

Below the execution plan, the Predicate Information is shown:

```
14 Predicate Information (identified by operation id):  
15 -----  
16  
17 1 - filter("TB1"."CAPACITY"<COUNT(*)
```

Plan hash value: 902696625

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		621K	182M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 1	FILTER					
2	HASH GROUP BY		621K	182M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 3	HASH JOIN		621K	182M	1114 (2)	00:00:01
4	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_LOCATIONS	70	20020	3 (0)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	621K	13M	1106 (2)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

- 1 - filter("TB1"."CAPACITY"<COUNT(*))
- 3 - access("TB2"."LOCATION_ID"="TB1"."LOCATION_ID")

Note

- dynamic statistics used: dynamic sampling (level=2)

I notice the transaction cost being "1156".

Modify the previous request to display locations where capacity was exceeded by at least 50%.
The data will be sorted by location.

```
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.location_id, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.location_id,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity + (tb1.capacity/2)
Order by
  tb1.location_id asc;
```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The Query Builder window contains the following SQL query:

```

1 Select
2   tb2.start_time_id, tb1.location_id, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
3 From
4   tbdw_sessions_history tb2
5 JOIN
6   tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
7 Group By
8   tb1.location_id,
9   tb1.state_name,
10  tb2.start_time_id,
11  tb1.capacity
12 Having
13   count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity + (tb1.capacity/2)
14 Order by

```

The Query Result window shows the following data:

START_TIME_ID	LOCATION_ID	STATE_NAME	NUMBER_OF_SESSIONS	CAPACITY
1 07-DEC-16	4	Iasi	23	15
2 26-AUG-06	23	Neamt	16	10
3 15-OCT-22	23	Neamt	17	10
4 25-MAR-02	67	Constanta	18	10
5 31-JUL-03	67	Constanta	16	10
6 07-DEC-06	67	Constanta	16	10
7 28-JAN-18	67	Constanta	17	10
8 12-MAY-19	67	Constanta	16	10
9 06-NOV-22	67	Constanta	20	10

I'm checking the cost.

```

explain plan
set statement_id = 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_2'
for
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.location_id, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.location_id,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity + (tb1.capacity/2)
Order by
  tb1.location_id asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_2', 'serial'));

```


Plan hash value: 2247675393

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		621K	105M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 1	FILTER					
2	SORT GROUP BY		621K	105M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 3	HASH JOIN		621K	105M	1114 (2)	00:00:01
4	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBW_LOCATIONS	70	10920	3 (0)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	621K	13M	1106 (2)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

- 1 - filter(COUNT(*)>"TB1"."CAPACITY"+"TB1"."CAPACITY"/2)
- 3 - access("TB2"."LOCATION_ID"="TB1"."LOCATION_ID")

Note

- dynamic statistics used: dynamic sampling (level=2)

I notice the transaction cost being "1156".

For the locations obtained in the previous point, determine if there is an upward trend in the last 5 years of increasing number of sessions. Sort the results by location, year, number of sessions in that year.

I will be using a **materialized view** to store the results from the previous request.

```

CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW tbdw_mv_locations_overflow_capacity1
  BUILD IMMEDIATE
  REFRESH COMPLETE
  ON DEMAND
  AS
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.location_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions,
tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.location_id,
  tb1.address,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity + (tb1.capacity/2)
Order by
  tb1.location_id asc;

```


3. Calculate the income for the last 10 years. Display the year and the total amount of income. Sort by year, descending.

```

select
  tb2.an, sum(tb1.price)
from
  tbdw_subscriptions_history tb1
join
  tbdw_time tb2 on tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
where
  tb2.an >= 2014
and
  tb2.an < 2024
group by
  tb2.an
order by
  tb2.an;

```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The left pane displays the database schema with tables like TB_STATES, TB_RESULTS, and TB_SESSIONS. The main window shows a query in the Worksheet:

```

1 select
2   tb2.an, sum(tb1.price)
3 from
4   tbdw_subscriptions_history tb1
5 join
6   tbdw_time tb2 on tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
7 where
8   tb2.an >= 2014
9 and
10  tb2.an < 2024
11 group by
12  tb2.an
13 order by

```

Below the query, the Query Result pane shows the following data:

AN	SUM(TB1.PRICE)
1 2014	475180
2 2015	449985
3 2016	462840
4 2017	470860
5 2018	472765
6 2019	430540
7 2020	436650
8 2021	469045
9 2022	493740
10 2023	53010

The status bar at the bottom indicates "All Rows Fetched: 10 in 0.04 seconds".

I'm checking the cost.

```

explain plan
set statement_id = 'dw_income_request_3'
for
select
  tb2.an, sum(tb1.price)
from
  tbdw_subscriptions_history tb1
join
  tbdw_time tb2 on tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
where

```

```

tb2.an >= 2014
and
tb2.an < 2024
group by
tb2.an
order by
tb2.an;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_income_request_3','serial'));

```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a query in the Worksheet:

```

9      tbdw_time tb2 on tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
10     where
11         tb2.an >= 2014
12     and
13         tb2.an < 2024
14     group by
15         tb2.an
16     order by
17         tb2.an;
18

```

Below the query, the Execution Plan is shown:

```

1 PLAN_TABLE_OUTPUT
2 Plan hash value: 647554590
3
4 Id | Operation | Name | Rows | Bytes | Cost (%CPU) | Time |
5 -----
6 0 | SELECT STATEMENT | | 14806 | 636K | 28 (11) | 00:00:01 |
7 1 | SORT GROUP BY | | 14806 | 636K | 28 (11) | 00:00:01 |
8 2 | NESTED LOOPS | | 14806 | 636K | 27 (8) | 00:00:01 |
9 3 | NESTED LOOPS | | 14806 | 636K | 27 (8) | 00:00:01 |
10 4 | TABLE ACCESS FULL | TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY | 14806 | 318K | 25 (0) | 00:00:01 |
11 * 5 | INDEX UNIQUE SCAN | TBW_TIME_ID_PK | 1 | | 0 (0) | 00:00:01 |
12 * 6 | TABLE ACCESS BY INDEX ROWID | TBW_TIME | 1 | 22 | 0 (0) | 00:00:01 |
13
14
15 Predicate Information (identified by operation id):
16

```

The left sidebar shows the database schema tree with various tables and views expanded under 'Tables (Filtered)'. The status bar at the bottom indicates 'All Rows Fetched: 23 in 0.247 seconds'.

Plan hash value: 647554590

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		14806	636K	28 (11)	00:00:01
1	SORT GROUP BY		14806	636K	28 (11)	00:00:01
2	NESTED LOOPS		14806	636K	27 (8)	00:00:01
3	NESTED LOOPS		14806	636K	27 (8)	00:00:01
4	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY	14806	318K	25 (0)	00:00:01
* 5	INDEX UNIQUE SCAN	TBDW_TIME_ID_PK	1		0 (0)	00:00:01
* 6	TABLE ACCESS BY INDEX ROWID	TBDW_TIME	1	22	0 (0)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

```
5 - access("TB1"."START_TIME_ID"="TB2"."TIMP_ID")
6 - filter("TB2"."AN">=2014 AND "TB2"."AN"<2024)
```

Note

```
- dynamic statistics used: dynamic sampling (level=2)
```

I notice the transaction cost being "28".

2.10.2 Example 2

Display the number of clients who prefer training sessions with male trainers and the number of clients who prefer training sessions with female trainers.

I am using a **materialized view** to count the number of sessions completed with a male trainer for each user.

```
CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW tbdw_mv_customers_preferred_trainer_male
BUILD IMMEDIATE
REFRESH COMPLETE
ON DEMAND
AS
select
  tb1.id, count(tb3.gender) as preferred_trainer_male
from
  tbdw_customers tb1
```

```

join
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2 on tb1.customer_id = tb2.customer_id
join
  tbdw_trainers tb3 on tb2.trainer_id = tb3.trainer_id
where
  tb3.gender = 'male'
group by
  tb1.id
order by
  tb1.id;

```


I am using a **materialized view** to count the number of sessions completed with a female trainer for each user.

```

CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW tbdw_mv_customers_prefered_trainer_female2
BUILD IMMEDIATE
REFRESH COMPLETE
ON DEMAND
AS
select
  tb1.id, count(tb3.gender) as prefered_trainer_female
from
  tbdw_customers tb1
join
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2 on tb1.customer_id = tb2.customer_id

```

```

join
  tbdw_trainers tb3 on tb2.trainer_id = tb3.trainer_id
where
  tb3.gender = 'female'
group by
  tb1.id
order by
  tb1.id;

```


I am using a **procedure** that uses the two previously defined views to calculate the number of clients who prefer training sessions with male trainers and the number of clients who prefer training sessions with female trainers.

I have also included the number of clients who have the same number of sessions regardless of the gender of the trainers.

```

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_customers_prefered_trainer AS
  min_id number;
  max_id number;
  pf_male number;
  pf_female number;
  pf_male_total number;
  pf_female_total number;
  pf_equal_total number;
BEGIN

```

```

BEGIN
  SELECT min(customer_id) into min_id FROM tbdw_customers;
  SELECT max(customer_id) into max_id FROM tbdw_customers;
EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    min_id := 0;
    max_id := 0;
END;

pf_male_total :=0;
pf_female_total :=0;
pf_equal_total :=0;

for contor in min_id..max_id
Loop
  BEGIN
  SELECT
    preferred_trainer_female into pf_female
  FROM
    tbdw_mv_customers_preferred_trainer_female2 tb1
  WHERE
    tb1.id = contor;
EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    pf_female := 0;
END;

  BEGIN
  SELECT
    preferred_trainer_male into pf_male
  FROM
    tbdw_mv_customers_preferred_trainer_male tb1
  WHERE
    tb1.id = contor;
EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    pf_male := 0;
END;

  if pf_male > pf_female then pf_male_total := pf_male_total+1; end if;
  if pf_male < pf_female then pf_female_total := pf_female_total+1; end if;
  if pf_male = pf_female then pf_equal_total := pf_equal_total+1; end if;

end Loop;

dbms_output.put_line ('Number of customers who prefer male trainers ' || pf_male_total);
dbms_output.put_line ('Number of customers who prefer female trainers ' || pf_female_total);
dbms_output.put_line ('Number of customers neutral ' || pf_equal_total);

```

```
END;  
/  
set serveroutput on;  
begin  
tbdw_customers_prefered_trainer;  
end;  
/
```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, the 'Connections' pane shows a tree view of database objects under 'DW_PROJECT3.1', including tables like TB_CITIES, TB_CONTRACTS, and TB_CUSTOMERS. The main workspace is in 'Query Builder' mode, showing a PL/SQL script for creating a procedure named 'tbdw_customers_prefered_trainer'. The script defines several numeric variables and uses a SELECT statement to populate 'min_id' and 'max_id' from the 'tbdw_customers' table. An EXCEPTION block handles the 'NO_DATA_FOUND' error by setting the variables to 0. Below the script, the 'Script Output' pane shows the message 'Procedure TBW_CUSTOMERS_PREFERRED_TRAINER compiled' and a completion time of 0.895 seconds.

```
1 CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_customers_prefered_trainer AS  
2   min_id number;  
3   max_id number;  
4   pf_male number;  
5   pf_female number;  
6   pf_male_total number;  
7   pf_female_total number;  
8   pf_equal_total number;  
9 BEGIN  
10  BEGIN  
11    SELECT min(customer_id) into min_id FROM tbdw_customers;  
12    SELECT max(customer_id) into max_id FROM tbdw_customers;  
13  EXCEPTION  
14    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN  
15      min_id := 0;  
16      max_id := 0;
```

Script Output x | Query Result x | Explain Plan x
Task completed in 0.895 seconds
Procedure TBW_CUSTOMERS_PREFERRED_TRAINER compiled

After running the procedure I have the following results.

“Number of customers who prefer male trainers 3017”

“Number of customers who prefer female trainers 632”

“Number of customers neutral 223”

From the results, I notice that clients predominantly chose male trainers.